

HORIZON-CL5-2023-D4-01 – GA 101138242

NEST InGrained ecosystem foR zEro EmissioN buildings

D1.1 NATIONAL AND EU REGULATIONS

Document Information	
Due Date:	30/06/2024
Actual resubmission Date:	17/04/26
Type of Deliverable (Report/Data/DEC/Ethics):	Report
Dissemination Level (Public/Sensitive)	Public
Prepared By:	NTUA
Version:	2

Disclaimer

This deliverable includes elements based on methodologies and background knowledge developed in previous EU-funded projects, in particular the H2020 project PLURAL (Grant Agreement No. 958218), coordinated by NTUA. Such elements concern the structure, categorisation, and presentation of regulatory analyses, as well as descriptions of common regulatory frameworks. Similarities concern the structure of the country chapters and the regulatory classification methodology applied in Chapter 4 and Chapter 5.

All project-specific content, analyses, and results have been independently developed within the GreenNest project.

This document's contents are not intended to replace the consultation of any applicable legal sources or the necessary advice of a legal expert, where appropriate. All information in this document is provided "as is" and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user, therefore, uses the information at its sole risk and liability. For the avoidance of all doubts, the European Commission has no liability in respect of this document, which is merely representing the authors' view.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of contents

1	Executive summary	7
2	Planned criteria	8
3	Introduction	9
3.1	Scope of the document	9
3.2	Contribution of other partners	9
3.3	Relation to other Activities and Deliverables in the Project.....	9
4	European Building Regulations	11
4.1	Categories of EU Regulations and related frameworks.....	11
4.1.1	Construction Products Regulation (CPR)	11
4.1.2	Revision of the CPR.....	13
4.1.3	Declaration of Performance and CE marking	14
4.2	Mechanical resistance, stability – Eurocodes	15
4.2.1	Eurocodes	15
4.2.2	National Implementation of the EN Eurocodes.....	16
4.2.3	Earthquake resistance	17
4.3	Fire safety	18
4.3.1	Euro-classification.....	19
4.4	Accessibility, safety in use, hygiene and health.....	22
4.5	Acoustics	22
4.6	Energy performance of buildings	23
4.7	Sustainable use of natural resources - Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) – Nature based/bio/recycled/reused materials.....	27
4.7.1	Environmental Product Declaration (EPD)	27
4.7.2	Sustainable Products and Ecodesign Directive	30
4.7.3	F-gas Regulation	31
4.8	Areas with lack of EU regulatory framework.....	31
5	National Regulations of demonstration countries	32
5.1	Germany	32
5.1.1	Basic characteristics of demonstration buildings	32
5.1.2	National regulations	34
5.1.3	Compliance challenges	59
5.2	Italy	61
5.2.1	Basic characteristics of demonstration building - DC#3 Delta demo in Porto Viro	61
5.2.2	National regulations	61
5.2.3	Compliance challenges	68

5.3	Greece.....	69
5.3.1	Basic characteristics of demonstration building - DC#4 North Aegean demo	69
5.3.2	National regulations	69
5.3.3	Compliance challenges	84
5.4	Other national standards and conclusions	86
5.4.1	Standards on earth construction from various countries.....	86
6	Deriving specifications for EU target markets	89
6.1	ZeB definition.....	89
6.2	Deriving ZeB Specifications.....	91
6.2.1	Basic requirements	91
6.2.2	Reduction of Embodied emissions	92
6.3	Target market definition.....	93
6.3.1	German target market.....	93
6.3.2	Italian target market.....	94
6.3.3	Greek target market	94
6.4	Standardization and certification	95
7	Conclusion.....	96
8	References	97
9	Annex.....	102
9.1	Annex I.....	102
9.2	Annex II	110
9.3	Annex III	114

List of figures

Figure 3.1: Relation with activities of the GreeNest project.....	10
Figure 6.1 Modular schematic of building life cycle stages according to EN:15978-2011.....	89
Figure 6.2:ZEB categories of Research Centre about zero emission buildings of Norway.....	90
Figure 6.3: EU interrelated Regulatory framework [39].	93

List of tables

Table 5.1: Fire resistance values (Greek Regulation)	73
Table 5.2: Category requirements of structural elements (Greek Regulation).....	73
Table 5.3: Fire Euroclasses of internal finishing (Greek Regulation).....	74
Table 5.4: Fire Euroclasses of external finishing (Greek Regulation)	74
Table 5.5: Acoustic comfort parameters (Greek Regulation)	77
Table 5.6: Thresholds for high acoustic comfort (Greek Regulation)	77
Table 5.7: Thresholds for normal acoustic comfort (Greek Regulation).....	78
Table 5.8: Maximum u-values for New buildings (Greek Regulation)	80
Table 5.9: Maximum Um values for New buildings (Greek Regulation)	80
Table 5.10: Maximum allowed PV system power (Greek Regulation).....	82
Table 5.11: Countries with standards/normative documents on earth construction	86
Table 6.1: Basic Requirements for ZeB	91
Table 9.1: Load bearing structures of DC#1 and respective regulation framework	102
Table 9.2: Non-Load bearing structures of DC#1 and respective regulation framework	105
Table 9.3: Non-Load bearing structures of DC#2 – EcoTechWall and respective regulation framework.....	110
Table 9.4: Load bearing structures of DC#4 and respective regulation framework	114
Table 9.5: Non -Load bearing structures of DC#4 and respective regulation framework	116

Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

CPD	Construction Products Directive
CPR	Construction Products Regulation
DC	Demo Case
DoP	Declaration of Performance
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive
EC	Eurocodes
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EPD	Environmental Product Declaration
ESPR	Ecodesign Sustainable Products Regulation
GA	Grant agreement
GWP	Global Warming Potential
LCA	Life Cycle Analysis
NDP	Nationally Determined Parameters
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
nZEB	nearly Zero Energy Building
ZeB	Zero emission Building

1 Executive summary

The GreeNest main objective is to develop, validate and promote an integrated solution based on a digitized platform to deliver a unified ecosystem comprising abiotic and biotic solutions aimed at facilitating the rapid and large-scale adoption of Zero Emission Buildings (ZeB).

The present report provides a review of the European and national regulatory frameworks applicable to new building construction. Emphasis is placed on Zero Emission Buildings (ZeB) and the sustainability of construction processes and materials. Recent amendments to the Construction Products Regulation (CPR), the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), and the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) constitute key regulatory developments introduced by the European Commission to support the achievement of the 2030 and 2050 climate and environmental objectives. In addition, the analysis identifies areas where the EU regulatory framework remains underdeveloped, particularly with regard to specific material categories such as bio-based and earth-based materials.

National regulations of the three countries, where the three demonstration case buildings are going to be constructed, were also reviewed and presented in a common template. Structural, load bearing and seismic, fire safety, acoustics, energy performance, health and safety, sustainable use of products and renewable energy sources are the main categories of the building related legislation and regulation framework that are provided. Basic requirements of the demonstration buildings based on all these regulatory frameworks must be specified from an early stage. Apart from providing guidance throughout the project, it will also support identifying any possible compliance challenges and take the appropriate measures and actions to overcome them. Major compliance challenges are identified and described. Finally, in the last chapter, basic specifications of the GreeNest demonstration buildings based on the EPBD ZeB definition is described together with the target market definition and the certification and standardization preliminary reference.

This deliverable builds upon established methodologies for regulatory analysis and the mapping of EU and national frameworks, including approaches developed in previous EU-funded projects. Certain structural elements and analytical approaches are informed by work carried out in the H2020 project PLURAL (Grant Agreement No. 958218), coordinated by NTUA. Such similarities arise from the use of common regulatory sources and standardised methodologies and do not concern project-specific results, which have been independently developed within the GreeNest project.

These elements reflect the use of common regulatory sources and established methodologies and do not concern project-specific results or original scientific contributions of GreeNest. All project-specific analyses, interpretations, and applications have been developed independently within GreeNest.

2 Planned criteria

This Task is landscaping the GreeNest ecosystem compliance with EU and country specific building regulations and codes with input from involved partners. Compliance with structural/wind load, energy performance, fire safety and acoustic performance must be ensured. The outcome of the task, reflected on the current report is technical and country specific and EU-wide building codes for defined target markets to guide the business development and the definition of realistic market applications for various EU building typologies. Codes related to ZeB are also presented. Testing and certification requirements will ensure that GreeNest ecosystem meets the compliance requirements with EU regulations.

This report is structured as follows: Chapter 4 presents the European regulatory framework, Chapter 5 reviews national regulations in the demonstration countries, and Chapter 6 defines ZeB specifications, target markets, and a preliminary certification strategy.

3 Introduction

3.1 Scope of the document

The scope of the current document is to provide a review of the regulatory framework at EU and national level on new building construction with the main focus on ZeB and the sustainable use of natural resources. Based on the requirements of the regulations, compliance challenges of demonstrator case buildings are identified. ZeB specifications for the DC buildings are derived based on the latest developments of the respective definition at EU level and in the frame of the project. Finally, the report provides a brief definition of the target markets based on the three different DCs and the countries of implementation.

3.2 Contribution of other partners

For the completion of the respective task the contribution of several partners was needed. Apart from leading the task from NTUA, significant input was provided by TUB, ZRS, INEB for German regulations and the Berlin demonstration cases data, MPV & BGTeC for Italian regulations and Porto Viro demonstration case. AMS provided input for the Greek demonstration case of North Aegean and PILI for the standardization and regulation status for earth-based materials.

3.3 Relation to other Activities and Deliverables in the Project

This report constitutes the first output of the project. Its primary objective is to map and analyse the EU and national regulatory frameworks related to Zero Emission Buildings (ZeB) and the sustainable use of construction resources, thereby establishing the basis for subsequent project activities. In this context, the development of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) builds directly on the findings of this report, as a number of the defined indicators are designed to reflect the performance and capabilities of the GreeNest ecosystem in alignment with the prevailing ZeB regulatory framework.

The next activity influenced by this report is “Preliminary Design By Inventory” (Figure 3.1) in which the preliminary design of the demonstrator buildings will have to comply with all the up-to-date regulation and codes of the EU and of the specific country. “Final design of ZeB demo sites implementing Design By Inventory and energetic assessment for ZeB status” will assure, based on the current work, that ZeB requirements are going to be met at the new constructions as well as all other building codes.

Any alternative designs that may occur in “SPs manufacturing and testing” and “Ecosystem demonstration and validation” in later work packages should be ensured that cover all regulation requirements reviewed in the current report

Finally, “Standardization and certification” will begin based on the preliminary roadmap of standardization and certification procedures (e.g. for construction products) of the current report as well as it will have in its disposal some of the basic SP commercial components connected with their standards.

FIGURE 3.1: RELATION WITH ACTIVITIES OF THE GREENEST PROJECT

4 European Building Regulations

This chapter is a review of all European regulations that set the framework for building construction and performance. Structural, fire safety, accessibility and hygiene as well acoustics regulations are presented. Emphasis is given at ZeB EU definition and the sustainability of new building construction which includes both energy and environmental performance.

4.1 Categories of EU Regulations and related frameworks

The European Union has put in place a comprehensive legislative and regulatory framework for the construction sector. Health and safety in construction and the free movement of engineering/construction services and products are important policy priorities. Concerning the construction activity itself, the focus is on the competitiveness of the sector, not least in the field of sustainable construction. [1]

European legislation defines the essential requirements that goods must meet when they are placed on the market and the European standardisation bodies have the task of drawing up the corresponding technical specifications. The free movement of products and services is now facilitated by the EU-wide implementation of common European technical standards for structural design: The Eurocodes.

The following Regulations and Directives are related to the EN Eurocodes:

- Construction Products Regulation;
- Public Procurement Directive;
- Services Directive;
- Directive on the provision of information in the field of technical standards and regulations.

4.1.1 Construction Products Regulation (CPR)

The Construction Products Directive of 1989 (CPD 89/106/EEC) was one of the first directives from the EU Commission to create a common framework for the regulations on buildings and construction products. It has been replaced by the Construction Products Regulation (CPR) and is legally binding throughout the EU. The objective of the Construction Products Regulation is to achieve the proper functioning of the internal market for construction products by establishing harmonised rules on how to express their performance.

The analytical structure follows the logic of the Construction Products Regulation (CPR), as also applied in similar studies such as the PLURAL project (GA No. 958218) [52].

The major key points of the CPR are:

- To set out the conditions for the marketing of construction products.

- To set out methods and criteria for assessing and expressing the performance of construction products, and the conditions for the use of CE marking.

Consequently, the CPR does not set directly any requirements for the construction products but establishes the rules of how and from where the requirements will occur. The aim of the CPR is to make the single market work better and improve the free movement of construction products in the EU, by laying down uniform rules for the marketing of these products and by providing a common technical language to assess the performance of construction products. In this way the regulation also enables EU countries to ensure the safety of construction works.

EU countries, on the other hand, are responsible for fire safety, mechanical resistance and stability, environmental, energy and other requirements applicable to construction works. Most of these requirements come from EU directives and frameworks so their approaches are quite common too.

As it is also stated in the Supporting study for the Review of the Construction Products Regulation: Evaluation [2]:

“The construction works, and consequently also the products used and integrated, are extensively influenced by the design as determined by the designer (architect, engineer, etc). Thus, design rules (building regulations) are set at Member State level (sometimes even at regional/local level) and are generally not related to the performance of an individual product but rather to the performance of the entire works (or a major feature of it) in which it is integrated”.

As it is mentioned before and to summarize, the CPR aims to achieve the proper functioning of the internal market for construction products by establishing rules on how to express the performance of construction products in relation to their essential characteristics and on the use of CE marking on those products.

Annex I to the CPR [3] lists [4]7 basic requirements for construction works. These basic requirements constitute the basis for the preparation of standardisation requests (mandates). Subject to normal maintenance, construction works must be designed and built in such a way as to satisfy the basic requirements for construction works for an economically reasonable working life, in the following areas:

1. *Mechanical resistance and stability*

The structure and construction products must ensure no collapses, deformations or damages to other structures or people.

2. *Safety in case of fire*

The structure and construction products must guarantee, in case of fire, the load-bearing capacity of the construction and limited fire propagation. Moreover, occupants and rescue teams' safety must be ensured.

3. *Hygiene, health and the environment*

Construction products must ensure, during their whole life cycle, the proper hygiene and good health condition to building occupants, as well as not causing emission of dangerous substances in construction, use and demolition phase.

4. *Safety and accessibility in use*

In general, construction products should guarantee that their use does not create risks of accidents or damages to the users. Moreover, accessibility for disabled persons must be taken into consideration.

5. *Protection against noise*

Occupants and nearby people should not be disturbed by construction products' noise emissions.

6. *Energy economy and heat retention*

Construction products must be designed and built in order to require low energy consumptions, both in construction, use and dismantling phases, aiming in general to energy-efficiency principles.

7. *Sustainable use of natural resources*

The reuse and recycling of the construction products, as well as their durability must be guaranteed.

This categorisation is derived from the essential requirements of CPR and is commonly used in regulatory analyses, including work done in the PLURAL project (GA No. 958218) [52]

It needs to be underlined that the above-mentioned basic works requirements, in spite of the word “requirements”, do not impose any obligations on anybody. They rather bring forward a categorization of the requirements Member States have defined or may define for construction works on their territory, and at the same time present the sphere of harmonization for CPR purposes, both these aspects to be taken duly into account when determining essential characteristics of construction products.

When the basic requirements of the CPR and CPD are compared, it may be seen that the CPR has a new requirement (No. 7 Sustainable use of natural resources), and that No. 3 (Hygiene, health and the environment) and No. 4 (Safety and accessibility in use) have been refined. This means that commercialisation of construction materials in Europe beyond 2013 stated to be subject of mandatory environmental assessment [4].

The CPR includes requirements for the sustainable use of natural resources (n7), the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions over the life cycle and the use of EPD for assessing and reporting the impacts of construction products (see section 1.8). If an EU Member State wishes to regulate in these areas of sustainability, it must use European standards where they exist when regulating and must withdraw national standards. This means that in the case of the CPR, a Member State must use the CEN/TC 350 suite of standards [5].

4.1.2 Revision of the CPR

Since 2016, partly guided by various European policies oriented to lead to a more sustainable future, procedures for a revision of the CPR has started. The other main reason for a revision was the non-creation of a single market for construction products. In conclusion, the two general objectives of the CPR revision are

to (1) achieve a well-functioning single market for construction products and to (2) contribute to the objectives of the green and digital transition, particularly the modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy.

The proposal for a revised CPR was adopted on 30 March 2022 and in July 2022 the consultation period ended. The main visions of the new CPR are around two axes:

Functioning of Single Market

- unlock the construction sector's growth and jobs potential
- improve the competitiveness of the sector
- digital transition of the construction ecosystem

Environmental Sustainability

- green transition of the manufacturing processes
- overall sustainability of the built environment
- efficient use of natural resources by facilitating reuse and recycling

In section 4.7 the part of the CPR addressing the sustainability performance of construction product is described together with the EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) and the new Ecodesign.

4.1.3 Declaration of Performance and CE marking

The Declaration of Performance is a key part of the Construction Products Regulation. It provides information on the performance of a product. Each construction product covered by a European harmonised standard or for which a European Technical Assessment has been issued needs this Declaration and has to be CE marked. This helps increase transparency and improves the functioning of the Single Market [6].

Where a manufacturer decides to place a construction product on the market and that product is covered by a harmonised standard or a European Technical Assessment has been issued for it, the manufacturer must draw up a Declaration of Performance which contains, among other things, the following information:

- product reference;
- systems of assessment and verification of consistency of performance of the product;
- reference of the applicable harmonised standard or European Technical Assessment;
- intended use or uses for the product;
- declared performance based on the assessment according to the applicable harmonised standard or European Technical Assessment.

Once the Declaration of Performance has been drawn up, the manufacturer must affix a CE marking to the product. The CE marking indicates that the performance of the product has been assessed and that it remains constant. CE marking enables a construction product to be placed legally on the market in any EU country

and then be traded on the EU's single market. EU countries must establish Product Contact Points for Construction to provide information on the requirements for construction products [7].

Based on the seven requirements for construction works and adopted in the CPR, as mentioned above, the regulation review will be continued examining other regulations at European level that are related with both construction products and the building as a whole.

4.2 Mechanical resistance, stability – Eurocodes

4.2.1 Eurocodes

Prior to the CPR, introduced in the previous section, and its predecessor the CPD (Construction Products Directive), the European Commission took the initiative to establish a set of harmonised technical rules for the design of construction works. The goal was these rules to gradually replace the national rules of member states. After the first generation of these European codes in the 1980s, the Commission decided to transfer the preparation and publication of the Eurocodes to the European Committee of Standardization (CEN) in order to be future standards.

By 2002, the Eurocodes have been developed and published as a series of ten European technical standards that provide a common approach to the structural design of buildings and other civil engineering works. They are the recommended reference for technical specifications in public contracts. The EN Eurocodes are expected to contribute to the establishment and functioning of the internal market for construction products and engineering services by eliminating the disparities that hinder their free circulation within the Community. Further, they are meant to lead to more uniform levels of safety in construction in Europe.

They are currently at the stage of maintenance and evolution in order to address the variety of new methods, new materials, new regulatory requirements and new societal needs developing and to extend harmonisation.

The Eurocodes apply to structural design of buildings and other civil engineering works including:

- geotechnical aspects
- structural fire design
- situations including earthquakes, execution and temporary structures

and they cover:

- basis of structural design (EN 1990)
- actions on structures (EN 1991)
- the design of concrete (EN 1992), steel (EN 1993), composite steel and concrete (EN 1994), timber (EN 1995), masonry (EN 1996) and aluminium (EN 1999) structures
- geotechnical design (EN 1997)
- the design, assessment and retrofitting of structures for earthquake resistance (EN 1998).

All of the EN Eurocodes relating to materials have a Part 1-1 which covers the design of buildings and other civil engineering structures and a Part 1-2 for fire design.

The EN Eurocodes are intended to be used as reference documents to determine the performance of construction products. They give a presumption of conformity with the basic requirements for mechanical resistance and stability, resistance to fire and safety in use.

The Member States of the EU and the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) recognise that EN Eurocodes serve as reference documents for the following purposes:

- as a means to prove compliance of building and civil engineering works with the basic requirements of the Construction Products Regulation, particularly Basic Requirement 1 "Mechanical resistance and stability" and Basic Requirement 2 "Safety in case of fire";
- as a basis for specifying contracts for construction works and related engineering services;
- as a framework for drawing up harmonised technical specifications for construction products (ENs and ETAs) [8].

The European Standardisation system relating to construction is a comprehensive system of design standards that comprises the EN Eurocodes, along with material and product standards, as well as execution and test standards.

4.2.2 National Implementation of the EN Eurocodes

Under the Public Procurement Directive, it is mandatory that Member States accept designs to the EN Eurocodes. The EN Eurocodes will become the standard technical specification for all public works contracts. If proposing an alternative design, one must demonstrate that is technically equivalent to an EN Eurocode solution.

The implementation of an EN Eurocode part has three phases, the Translation Period, the National Calibration Period and the Coexistence period. Every country – member state of the EU had to make an implementation plan for the Eurocodes in order to translate every part made available, to set the National Determined Parameters to be applied, to publish the national standard transposing each Eurocode and finally to adapt national provisions that Eurocodes can be used for specifying contracts for the execution of public construction works and related engineering services.

EN Eurocodes recognise the responsibility of regulatory authorities in each Member State and have safeguarded their right to determine values related to regulatory safety matters at a national level where these continue to vary from State to State. EN Eurocodes provide for National Choices full sets of recommended values, classes, symbols and alternative methods to be used as Nationally Determined Parameters (NDPs).

During the Coexistence Period which can last up to a maximum time of three years after the national publication of the last Part of a Package, both the National Standard transposing the EN Eurocode and any existing national standard can be used. At the end of the Coexistence Period of the last EN Eurocode Part of a Package, the National Standardisation Bodies should withdraw all conflicting National Standards [9].

As the National Standardisation Bodies are not expected to maintain the withdrawn National standards in practice, there will be little option but to use the EN Eurocodes. It is generally intended and expected that pressures from international clients and contractors, as well as other stakeholders like the insurance industry, will lead to their more rapid application for private construction [8].

Eurocodes generally deal with structural issues of buildings and infrastructure while the suggested and under development solutions in the PLURAL project [52] are prefabricated external facades or internal “add-ons”. However, the timber frame of the external Wall Heating and Cooling that will be deployed in the Czech demo building, may be related for example with Eurocode 5 (Design of timber structures) and the ventilated façade of the Spanish demo building is a metallic structure related to Eurocode 3 (Design of steel structures).

4.2.3 Earthquake resistance

The first European standard for seismic design was first published in 2000 as Eurocode 8 (also denoted by EN 1998): “Design of structures for earthquake resistance”. It covers common structures and, although its provisions are of general validity, special structures, such as nuclear power plants, large dams or offshore structures are beyond its scope. Its seismic design should satisfy additional requirements and be subject to complementary verifications. Like all standards it has been replaced and amended since its first publication.

The objectives of seismic design in accordance with Eurocode 8 are explicitly stated. Its purpose is to ensure that in the event of earthquakes:

- *human lives are protected;*
- *damage is limited; and*
- *structures important for civil protection remain operational.*

These objectives are present throughout the code and condition the principles and application rules therein included.

Eurocode 8 is composed by 6 parts dealing with different types of constructions or subjects:

1. General rules, seismic actions and rules for buildings
2. Bridges
3. Assessment and retrofitting of buildings
4. Silos, tanks and pipelines
5. Foundations, retaining structures and geotechnical aspects
6. Towers, masts and chimneys

Although the Eurocodes are the same across the different countries, for matters related to safety and economy or for aspects of geographic or climatic nature national adaptation is allowed if therein explicitly

foreseen. These are the Nationally Determined Parameters (NDPs) that are listed at the beginning of each Eurocode. For these parameters, each country, in a National Annex included in the corresponding National Standard, may take a position, either keeping or modifying them.

4.3 Fire safety

Until recently EU countries had different methods for testing and classifying the Reaction to Fire performance of construction materials. This made comparison of the resulting data extremely difficult, with manufacturers required to carry out different tests in order to sell their products in a particular country. The implementation of a single classification system across the EU member states has introduced a common method for comparing the Reaction to Fire performance of construction products. Testing is standardised through the use of EN 13501-1: Fire classification of construction products and building elements. For construction products intended to be used in wall and ceiling assemblies, there are seven Reaction to Fire classification levels available – A1, A2, B, C, D, E and F. Additional criteria provide information on a product’s tendency to produce smoke and flaming droplets or particles. For combustible products, smoke release is an important consideration and is measured for Reaction to Fire classes A2 to D. There are three smoke intensity levels: s1, s2 and s3, with s3 being the worst. Burning droplets/particles can inflict skin burns and cause further spread of fire. Burning droplets/particles are measured for Reaction to Fire classes A2 to E. There are three classes of burning droplets: d0, d1 and d2, with d2 being the worst.

The European reaction to fire classification system was introduced in support of the Construction Products Directive (CPD) with the aim of achieving harmonisation and eventually replacing the different national standard tests and classifications. Some correlations could indeed be drawn between the 7 Euroclasses and elements of the pre-existing standards. Although the CPD is now replaced by the CPR, the European harmonised test methods and classifications remain the same.

Harmonising test standards in the European Union is meaningful whilst aiming for simplification and standardisation. However, the intended use, as described in the CPR, translates into different fields of application. Consequently, the test results have to be interpreted and assessed in order to confirm a fire classification, including the boundary conditions. These currently fall into two categories: the direct field of application (DIAP) and the extended field of application (EXAP).

Essentially, the harmonised tests and standards are in place, but it is still a matter for each Member State to decide for itself what level of classification for fire safety is considered acceptable for each type of application.

Fire regulations historically refer to three basic categories of fire standards: Reaction to fire, resistance to fire and external fire performance of roofs. A fourth category is used in a number of countries and currently research is going on for setting a European approach to “external fire on façades”. This was triggered by the introduction of new façade systems in buildings and their growing importance.

4.3.1 Euro-classification

The European standard that provides classification of products in relation with their performance in fire exposure is the EN 13501 standard with 6 separate parts categorizing different type of products. It was first released in 2002 and various versions followed. The various standard parts provide the fire classification procedure for either fire reaction or fire resistance, depending also on the type of product.

Reaction to Fire

A reaction to fire test assesses how easily a product can be ignited and contribute to fire growth. It relates mostly to the early stages of a fire development and is arguably mostly relevant to those products directly exposed to the fire source i.e. wall linings, ceiling linings and external wall surfaces. It is also relevant for assessing the performance of construction products during construction or during building maintenance, e.g. welding of the building elements.

Standard EN 13501 part 1, provides the reaction to fire classification procedure for all construction products, including products incorporated within building elements. Products are considered in relation to their end use application and are divided in three categories:

- construction products, excluding floorings and linear pipe thermal insulation products;
- floorings;
- linear pipe thermal insulation products.

The products are tested with specific test methods and according to their performance they are classified into seven Euroclasses:

- A1 and A2 for non-combustible materials
- B, C, D, E for materials that range from limited to high contribution to fire
- F for materials which fail Euroclass E criteria and are considered flammable.

Further classifications (typically associated with reaction to fire classes D – B) are used to indicate smoke production (from s1 (little or no smoke) to s3 (substantial smoke)) and flaming droplets/particles (from d0 (none) to d2 (quite a lot)).

Alongside the Euroclass system there is now a European test to assess the smouldering or continuous glowing potential of a product (EN 16733). Smouldering or continuous glowing represent slow, internal combustion processes that can lead to fires breaking out some distance and time away from the original source of ignition. This characteristic is considered a risk, regarding hidden spread of fire and persistence of ignition sources after fire brigades have assumed that a fire is completely extinguished.

Resistance to fire

One definition of fire resistance is “the ability of a structural element to sustain the performance of its structural duty, whilst being exposed to the temperatures likely to be encountered in a developed fire for specified periods of time.”

As it was described in section 1.2 of this report, the Eurocodes (EN 1991 General Actions and the relating to specific material ones: EN 1992, 1993, 1994, 1995, 1996 1999) have a dedicated part (Part 1-2) for fire design. The fire parts of Structural Eurocodes deal with specific aspects of passive fire protection in terms of designing structures and parts thereof for adequate load bearing resistance and for limiting fire spread as relevant. These parts of the Eurocodes deal only with passive methods of fire protection. Active methods are not covered.

In the EN 1991-1-2 the terms: load bearing function – R, Integrity – E, and Insulation – I, are mentioned. Then they are also defined in the EN 13501-2 where the classifications for resistance to fire are described together with the parts 3 and 4 for other type building components and systems. According to the EN 13501-2:

R - Loadbearing capacity is the ability of the element of construction to withstand fire exposure under specified mechanical actions, on one or more faces, for a period of time, without any loss of structural stability. The criteria which provide for assessment of imminent collapse will vary as a function of the type of loadbearing element (columns, walls, floors, roofs)

E - Integrity is the ability of the element of construction that has a separating function, to withstand fire exposure on one side only, without the transmission of fire to the unexposed side as a result of the passage of flames or hot gases. They may cause ignition either of the unexposed surface or of any material adjacent to that surface.

I - Thermal insulation is the ability of the element of construction to withstand fire exposure on one side only, without the transmission of fire as a result of significant transfer of heat from the exposed side to the unexposed side. Transmission shall be limited so that neither the unexposed surface nor any material in close proximity to that surface is ignited. The element shall also provide a barrier to heat, sufficient to protect people near to it.

Consequently, resistance to fire relates to the structure, which mostly is a combination of products including fixing methods. However, it could consist of a single or composite product. Accreditation is therefore awarded to that particular construction as a whole, and not to the individual products it is made of. With this kind of testing, there are many possible different combinations of products and fixings making up the overall structure, and it is impractical to test every permutation. Because of the huge variations that are possible, harmonised standards are accompanied by direct and extended field of application rules.

The most relevant test standards are EN 1363, EN 1364, EN 1365 and EN 1366.

The results are expressed as the number of minutes that all, or several of these three aspects resist the effects of a fire, so an element fulfilling all of these criteria for 30 minutes would be classified as REI 30. The classifications for resistance to fire are described in EN 13501-2, 3 and 4. Because the test sample has to represent the complete element, roof or wall, etc. determining REI requires testing in large scale and is expensive. For example, a flat roof test would need to include the supporting roof deck, the waterproofing layer as well as the insulation respecting the method of fixing intended in the building. Naturally, the degree to which the insulation has an opportunity to play a role in fire resistance depends on the construction. For instance, if a flat roof with a concrete slab base were being tested, it would give several hours of fire resistance, regardless of what other products were placed on top, and when it does fail, the performance of the effect of the other products would be irrelevant as the structure itself would already be compromised.

Fire tests for Facades

In the past, most countries set requirements for outer façade insulation based on the classifications obtained from the standard “reaction to fire” laboratory tests. Experience has shown that, in some cases, these tests do not give sufficient information about the performance of the complete insulation system in a real fire. So, dedicated full scale “façade fire” tests have been developed in several European countries. Most of these tests are based on the scenario of a fire in a room breaking through a window. In most cases, the parameters measured include the observation of flame spread (visual observation and temperature measurements), the assessment of damage on the outside of and within the insulation system after the test, and burning droplets and parts or debris falling down. However, there are large differences between the tests depending on the country. The main parameters, which are different, include the following:

- Type of fire source (some tests use wood cribs, others gas burners or liquid fuels)
- Size of fire source
- Specimen configuration (corner or flat wall, additional openings/windows)
- Height of test rig

Various tests are used for different height limitations in different countries.

The European Commission started a new project in 2017 with the aim to develop a European approach to assess the fire performance of facades and the definition of all relevant details and classifications to be used for harmonised products standards (in CEN) and for European Assessment Documents (in EOT A) for the relevant construction products (kits) within the framework of implementation of the Construction Products Regulation (CPR) 305/2011/EU. As a result of this project in 2018, a study (*Development of a European approach to assess the fire performance of facades*, [10]) was published which still does not deliver a final solution. Two possibilities for the future European method were presented, representing two different approaches.

The European Commission decided in autumn 2019 to go forward with the “alternative approach”. A study was started with the goal to finalize this assessment method, develop assessment criteria and classifications and verify repeatability and reproducibility of test results. The European Commission could introduce this new method for CE marking with a delegated act. The study is envisaged for a time period of 2 years and started in April 2020. [11]

It is not clear, how in the end member states will adopt this method for façade systems, as the European Commission can only decide how to deal with products and kits which are CE marked [12].

4.4 Accessibility, safety in use, hygiene and health

Safety and accessibility in buildings on European regulatory level exists only at a strategy level for accessibility issues in public buildings. In March 2021, the European Commission published the EU Strategy for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2021-2030. This is the second strategy of this kind, and builds upon the work done on the basis of the European Disability Strategy 2010-2020. In this first strategy a key feature of the commitments made was to ensure ensuring accessibility of the built environment [13].

Accessibility to the physical environment, including buildings, is required by Article 9 of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) and was adopted by most European countries. The latest strategy of 2021-2030 underlines the need for cooperation between the EU and the national frameworks. As it refers mostly to public buildings, national regulation concerning this issue will not be reviewed.

Apart from the CPR approach regarding hygiene, health and the environment (“Construction products must ensure, during their whole life cycle, the proper hygiene and good health condition to building occupants, as well as not causing emission of dangerous substances in construction, use and demolition phase”), this category applies also to a building scale as indoor environmental conditions.

Although the EPBD indicates that indoor climate conditions shall be taken into account when putting minimum energy requirements in place, within the EU legislation there are currently no clear requirements describing how this can be achieved. The European Committee for Standardization has issued the following non-mandatory standards with regard to IAQ: EN 13779: Ventilation for non-residential buildings. Performance requirements for ventilation, air conditioning and cooling systems; and EN 15251: Indoor environmental input parameters for design and assessment of the energy performance of buildings, addressing indoor air quality, thermal environment, lighting and acoustics.

4.5 Acoustics

On European level, the noise policy relates to environmental noise. EU does not have yet a policy on noise in buildings, e.g. neighbour noise is not included in the EU Noise Policy. Concerning national noise policies, they relate typically to the EU policy and thus in general to environmental noise only. Environmental noise is

regulated at EU level at the source of the noise, with legislation on issues such as harmonized noise limits for motor vehicles, outdoor equipment and other noise-generating products. [14], [15]

Acoustic regulations for housing, educational buildings and some other building categories now exist in most countries in Europe, but findings from comparative studies show that extent and strictness as well as descriptors vary considerably across Europe. The acoustic performance areas dealt with are e.g. airborne and impact sound insulation, reverberation time, traffic noise, service equipment noise. Comparing countries, there is in general no consistency of contents, structure or enforcement of acoustic regulations [16].

4.6 Energy performance of buildings

Buildings are responsible for approximately 40 % of energy consumption and 36 % of CO₂ emissions in the EU. The Commission sets all the appropriate building performance regulatory framework for its member states, mostly in the form of directives, in order to achieve energy consumption and emission reduction targets.

The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) (EUR-Lex, 2010) and the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) (EUR Lex, 2012) are the EU's main legislative frameworks promoting the improvement of the energy performance of buildings within the EU. The Renewable Energy Directive (Directive 2018/2001/EU) can be also added as the 2018 version, upgraded the one of 2009 including articles related to RES in buildings. These directives provide policies for achieving a highly energy efficient and decarbonised building stock while creating a stable environment for investment decisions to be taken enabling consumers and businesses to make more informed choices to save energy and money. Actually, the EPBD replaced the first directive dedicated on the energy performance of buildings that was published in 2002 (Directive 2002/91/EC) in the interest of clarity and to raise the bar to a higher level by introducing the ambitious concept of nearly-zero energy consuming buildings and including Renewable Energy systems. Both EPBD and EED were amended, as part of the Clean energy for all Europeans package, in 2018 and 2019 respectively while a recast of the EPBD in 2024 and a revised EED in 2023 are the current versions.

EPBD

By the beginning of the GreeNest project the EU has proposed to move from the current nearly zero-energy buildings to zero-emission buildings by 2030. This happened when the Commission submitted to the European Parliament and the Council a proposal for another recast of the EPBD on 15 December 2021. The directive forms part of the 'Fit for 55' package, setting the vision for achieving a zero-emission buildings stock by 2050.

In April 2024 European Council formally adopted the recast EPBD (EU/2024/1275) which enhances the energy performance requirements for new buildings. It requires all new residential and non-residential buildings to be **zero-emission buildings** as of 1 January 2028 for buildings owned by public bodies and 1 January 2030 for

all other new buildings, with the possibility for specific exemptions. According to the revised directive, a zero-emission building has no on-site carbon emissions from fossil fuels and a very high energy performance.

As for nearly-zero energy buildings, the very small amount of energy still required for zero-emission buildings is covered by energy from on-site and nearby renewable energy sources, including from renewable energy communities and efficient district heating and cooling (in accordance with the 2023 Energy Efficiency Directive). Zero-emission buildings will also support grid flexibility, by providing decentralised renewable energy generation at household or community level, electric and thermal energy storage, better demand response and smart charging, which will reduce demand and contribute to the overall energy grid supply.

Zero-emission building definitions can be found in the international literature with only a few given by national legislation. The majority of them are conceptual and developed and studied at a theoretical level. A general consensus is that a Zero-Emission Building (ZeB) is an energy efficient building that produces enough renewable energy to compensate for its GHG emissions [17].

According to the recast EPBD definition:

“Zero-emission Building” (ZeB) means a building with a very high energy performance, as determined in accordance with Annex I, requiring zero or a very low amount of energy, producing zero on-site carbon emissions from fossil fuels and producing zero or a very low amount of operational greenhouse gas emissions, in accordance with Article 11 of the recast.

Article 11 specifies the definition with a few more characteristics and obligations that ZeB should have. The strictest and most straightforward one has to do with the zero on-site carbon emissions which is already included in the general definition. The second one is that a ZeB should also where economically and technically feasible, offer the capacity to react to external signals and adapt its energy use, generation or storage. The rest of requirements have to do with thresholds of the energy demand and the operational greenhouse emissions of a ZeB and they are left to the member states to determine and quantify. However, a ZeB should have at least 10% less energy demand than the nZEB in every country. In addition, thresholds should be set for the operational greenhouse emissions that can be differentiated between new and existing buildings.

The recast EPBD sets two basic requirements related to when new buildings in the member states should comply with ZeB definition. The first is that:

- a) as of 1st January 2028, all new buildings owned by public bodies
- b) as of 1st January 2030, all new buildings

should be zero-emission buildings.

The second requirement includes the calculation of **life-cycle Global Warming Potential (GWP)** and its disclosure through the Energy Performance Building Certificate (EPBC). All new buildings with the following properties should comply with it:

- a) as of 1st January 2028, all new buildings with a useful floor area larger than 2000 m²
- b) as of 1st January 2030, all new buildings

In conclusion, while the focus of the recast EPBD is the reduction of operational greenhouse gas emissions, ZeB definition further includes the calculation of life-cycle GWP and its disclosure through the EPBC.

In ANNEX III of the recast EPBD, the calculation of the life-cycle GWP is explained and are given guidelines of what documentation, standards and databases should be used. The total life-cycle GWP of a new building is consisted of a numeric indicator for each life-cycle stage and is expressed as kgCO₂eq / (m² useful floor area) calculated over a period of 50 years. The data selection, scenario definition and calculations shall be carried out in accordance with EN 15978 (EN 15978:2011 Sustainability of construction works. Assessment of environmental performance of buildings. Calculation method). Finally, the scope of all building elements is as defined in the Level(s) common EU framework for indicator 1.2. [18]

Energy Efficiency Directive (EED)

The 2012 Energy Efficiency Directive established a set of binding measures to help the EU reach its 20% energy efficiency target by 2020. Under the Directive, all EU countries are required to use energy more efficiently at all stages of the energy chain, from production to final consumption.

Energy efficiency plays a vital role in reducing the impact of energy costs on business and domestic consumers. It lessens carbon emissions and decreases our dependence on fossil fuels, thereby improving our competitiveness and sustaining jobs. Achieving greater efficiency in resource inputs and minimising waste also improves productivity and reduces costs.

In the context of the Energy Efficiency Directive, a number of important measures have been adopted throughout the EU to improve energy efficiency in Europe, including

- policy measures to achieve energy savings equivalent to annual reduction of 1.5% in national energy sales
- EU countries making energy efficient renovations to at least 3% per year of buildings owned and occupied by central governments
- national long-term renovation strategies for the building stock in each EU country
- mandatory energy efficiency certificates accompanying the sale and rental of buildings
- the preparation of national energy efficiency action plans (NEEAPs) every three years
- minimum energy efficiency standards and labelling for a variety of products such as boilers, household appliances, lighting and televisions (energy label and ecodesign)
- the planned rollout of close to 200 million smart meters for electricity and 45 million for gas by 2020

- obligation schemes for energy companies to achieve yearly energy savings of 1.5% of annual sales to final consumers
- large companies conducting energy audits at least every four years
- protecting the rights of consumers to receive easy and free access to data on real-time and historical energy consumption

The Commission also published guidelines on good practice in energy efficiency.

On 30 November 2016 the Commission proposed an update to the Energy Efficiency Directive, including a new 30% energy efficiency target for 2030, and measures to update the Directive to make sure the new target is met (Energy Efficiency Directive, 2018). Finally, in October 2023 based on the 2021 recast proposal as part of the Green Deal package and further as part of 2022 REPowerEU plan, the Commission has revised the Energy Efficiency Directive, together with other energy and climate rules.

The Revised EED (EU/2023/1791) establishes ‘energy efficiency first’ as a fundamental principle of EU energy policy, giving it legal-standing for the first time. In practical terms, this means that energy efficiency must be considered by EU countries in all relevant policy and major investment decisions taken in the energy and non-energy sectors. [19] In addition, it raises the EU energy efficiency target agreeing on a collectively additional reduction in energy consumption by 2030 from EU countries.

Renewable Energy Directive

The Renewable Energy Directive is in general the legal framework for the development of renewable energy across all sectors of the EU economy. It establishes common principles and rules to remove barriers, stimulate investments and drive cost reductions in renewable energy technologies, and empowers citizens, consumers and businesses to participate in the clean energy transformation. The first Renewable Energy Directive was released in 2009 setting European (20% by 2020) and national binding targets.

In 2018 the new Renewable Energy Directive (2018/2001/EU) came into force aimed at keeping the EU a global leader in renewables and helping the EU to meet its emissions reduction commitments under the Paris Agreement.

Building on the 20% target for 2020, it established a new binding renewable energy target for the EU for 2030 of at least 32%, with a clause for a possible upwards revision by 2023, and comprises measures for the different sectors to make it happen. This Directive underlined the obligation of the member states to introduce measures in their building regulations and codes in order to increase the share of all kinds of energy from renewable sources in the building sector. This included in particular new provisions to enable citizens to play an active role in the development of renewables - enabling renewable energy communities and self-consumption of renewable energy, an increased 14 % target for the share of renewable fuels in transport by 2030 and strengthened criteria for ensuring bioenergy sustainability.

In July 2021, the Commission presented a proposal for a revised directive, as part of the package to deliver on the European Green Deal. After REPowerEU Plan proposed a raise to the renewable energy target, in

November 2023 the Revised EED (EU/2023/2413) came into force with an 18-month period for national transpositions in EU members. The directive basically doubled the target for renewable share by 2030 (42.5%) and laid a policy framework to facilitate electrification in many different sectors like heating and cooling, transport, industry, buildings and district heating/cooling as well as electric vehicles and recharging.

4.7 Sustainable use of natural resources - Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) – Nature based/bio/recycled/reused materials

According to the previous section, it can be derived in a simplified manner, that focusing on energy consumption reduction in buildings gradually gives its place to CO₂ emissions reduction and consequently to embedded emissions reduction of building elements and materials in terms of the indicator that represents the impact of a building to the environment and climate change. However, the environmental impact of constructing a new building is not only emissions embedded in the materials or emitted in the construction stage. Adopting eco-friendlier materials reduces intervention to the environment due to raw materials extraction, mitigates sources depletion and contributes to more sustainable stages of all building life cycle.

The basic requirement about the sustainable use of natural resources as described in the CPR has to do with the recyclability of construction works, their materials and parts after demolition, the durability of construction works and the use of environmentally compatible raw and secondary materials in construction works. And continues: For the assessment of the sustainable use of resources and of the impact of construction works on the environment, Environmental Product Declarations should be used when available. Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 of the European parliament (with latest amendment in 2021) lies down harmonised conditions for the marketing of construction products and repealing Council Directive 89/106/EEC.

Apart from amending existing directives towards a more sustainable use of resources, regulations like the EU Taxonomy and the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) are influencing the landscape, introducing elements like circularity and biodiversity reporting for large businesses.

4.7.1 Environmental Product Declaration (EPD)

An Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) is defined by International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 14025 as a Type III declaration that "quantifies environmental information on the life cycle of a product to enable comparisons between products fulfilling the same function." The EPD methodology is based on the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) tool that follows ISO series 14040.

An EPD report tells the life cycle story of a product in a single, comprehensive report. The EPD provides information about a product's impact upon the environment, such as global warming potential and impacts to air, soil and water bodies (smog creation, ozone depletion, water pollution etc). EPDs do not rank products, and the existence of an EPD for a product does not indicate that environmental performance criteria have been met. EPDs are a disclosure tool that helps purchasers to better understand a product's sustainable

qualities and environmental repercussions, so they can make more informed product selections. EPDs can be developed after a product life cycle assessment (LCA) is conducted and are based on applicable product category rules (PCRs).

EPDs provide a standard way of declaring the impacts of manufacturing and using products through Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). Construction products are assessed using a single set of Product Category Rules (PCR) ensuring consistent reporting for similar products. EPD for construction products in Europe use the European Standard, EN 15804, as their PCR, to ensure that the information is provided using the same LCA rules, with the same environmental indicators, and in a way that means the information for lots of different products can be brought together to provide the environmental impacts for a building. EPD should always be independently verified by an expert familiar with the product category. [20] [21]

The PCR:

- defines the parameters to be declared and the way in which they are collated and reported,
- describes which stages of a product's life cycle are considered in the EPD and which processes are to be included in the life cycle stages,
- defines rules for the development of scenarios,
- includes the rules for calculating the Life Cycle Inventory and the Life Cycle Impact Assessment underlying the EPD, including the specification of the data quality to be applied,
- includes the rules for reporting predetermined, environmental and health information, that is not covered by LCA for a product, construction process and construction service where necessary,
- defines the conditions under which construction products can be compared based on the information provided by EPD.

Within the construction industry, EPDs support carbon emission reduction by making it possible to compare the impacts of different materials and products in order to select the most sustainable option. Architects, engineers and designers are able to choose the most sustainable option for their project. Manufacturers are able to optimize the impact of their products and market their carbon transparency. An EPD is usually valid for five years, and is generated according to the relevant standards.

As previously mentioned, CPR was revised and basically made the EPD mandatory for all construction products [21]. More specifically:

Every construction product sold within the EU will need to disclose its Global Warming Potential (GWP) under the revised CPR, enabling architects, engineers, and developers to take informed decisions for their projects. However, this is just a first step. By 2030 manufacturers will be expected to report the full range of environmental impact data contained within EN 15804-based Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs).

EPDs provide transparent and comparable information about the life-cycle environmental impact of products within specific product categories.

The disclosures mentioned above are expected to be part of a digital product passport system, set out in the revised CPR, similar to the proposals for the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation.

Digital product passports will consist of a declaration of performance (DoP), providing comprehensive details on construction products, encompassing its performance characteristics, safety specifications, and environmental footprint. This aims to eliminate information silos and empowers stakeholders across the entire value chain, from architects and engineers to contractors and building inspectors.

EN 15804-compliant EPDs can be used to provide environmental performance information in a DoP.

The environmental data held within a declaration of performance must be third-party-verified by a Notified Body. The Notified Body will be required to: verify the manufacturer's initial and updated assessment; validate the process applied to generate that assessment; and verify the methodology used.

An EPD is just a way of providing environmental information about the product – products with high impacts can have EPD just like products with low impacts – but an EPD does give you the information to assess the product's performance at the building level. It's important to take into account the other products that you will need to produce the required functionality at the building level – two insulation products may have different conductivities so you will need less of one to provide the same amount of insulation – you will need to consider both the quantity of each insulation and the impact provided in the EPD to understand which product will have the better environmental performance.

In order to enhance harmonization, the main Program Operators for EPD verification in the construction sector created the Association ECO Platform, with members from different European countries.

Environmental data is now a mandatory requirement for manufacturers under the Construction Product Regulation (CPR). Aligned with EPD standards, this regulation imposes compulsory indicators, marking a significant stride toward harmonization. Member states are obligated to adhere to these standards, eliminating disparate regulations. The CPR not only streamlines data verification but also tackles anti-competitive practices hindering market access for foreign companies. Its enforcement is poised to nullify varying national rules, fostering a truly competitive market for sustainable construction products. This change is anticipated to bring about sustainability gains and reduce bureaucratic obstacles.

Following the provisional agreement reached in December, the revised CPR is expected to be published in the Official Journal later this year, likely by March 2024. At this point it becomes a binding and directly applicable law for member states. However, the current rules, including existing standards, will remain in force until 2039: a 15-year grace period following the new law's expected publication later in 2024 [22].

4.7.2 Sustainable Products and Ecodesign Directive

On 30 March 2022, the Commission adopted a package of measures to make sustainable products the norm in the EU and leave behind the current model of “take-make-dispose”. Addressing the environmental impact of products throughout their life-cycle and extending their lifetime will lead to more sustainable, circular and more resource-efficient products in the EU.

One of the proposed measures was to replace the current Ecodesign Directive with the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) introducing more Ecodesign criteria for a broader range of products. It aims to make sustainable products the norm on the EU market.

The current Ecodesign Directive 2009/125/EC has a long track record of delivering benefits to businesses, consumers and the environment. In 2021 alone, the impact of the current Ecodesign measures, covering 31 product groups, saved EUR 120 billion in energy expenditure for EU consumers and led to a 10% lower annual energy consumption by the products in scope.

The proposal for a new Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), published on 30 March 2022, is the cornerstone of the Commission’s approach to more environmentally sustainable and circular products. The proposal builds on the existing Ecodesign Directive, which currently only covers energy-related products.

The proposal establishes a framework to set Ecodesign requirements for specific product groups to significantly improve their circularity, energy performance and other environmental sustainability aspects. It will enable the setting of performance and information requirements for almost all categories of physical goods placed on the EU market, including also intermediate products that are used in manufacturing of other goods.

The requirements of the framework will cover a wide range including:

- product durability, reusability, upgradability and reparability
- presence of substances that inhibit circularity
- energy and resource efficiency
- recycled content
- remanufacturing and recycling
- carbon and environmental footprints
- information requirements, including a Digital Product Passport

The empowerment of the new ESPR will be done through delegated acts that will include Ecodesign requirements, conformity assessment procedures and any other additional requirements.

Based on the fact that the scope of the ESPR will include all kinds of products, it is possible that will also include construction products. Based on ESPR information session, the new Ecodesign will function as a safety net for keeping requirements of such products in desired levels if the CPR does not do so.

However, energy related products that are also construction products (as they are used in buildings) such as boilers, heat pumps, ventilations systems etc., will be primarily regulated by ESPR. On the other hand, CPR may regulate other aspects of such products, like safety. In that case the two regulations will be complementary. In addition, ESPR will have priority for setting sustainability requirements for intermediate construction products like cement. [23] [24]

4.7.3 F-gas Regulation

Refrigerant gases are known for their high GWP and as their usage very significant for all buildings. Replacing old f-gases with new ones that have less GWP and are not fluorinated contributes to the reduce of the global warming effect as well as the ozone layer depletion. The new F-Gas Regulation (EU) 2024/573 which came to replace the 2014 one, has been published in the Official Journal of the European Union and is in force from March 2024. The new Regulation establishes the total elimination of hydrofluorocarbons by 2050. Some very common refrigerant gases like R32 are going to gradually phase out and R290 is coming into use. Apart from having a lot less GWP, R290 is more energy efficient than R32, meaning that less electricity is needed to be consumed for the same heating or cooling.

4.8 Areas with lack of EU regulatory framework

As the latest EU building constructions regulatory framework evolves towards minimizing all kinds of emissions and reducing waste traditional building methods are surfacing again as they can provide some advantages in terms of sustainability. Some of these methods utilise earth-based material (like clay, rammed earth, earth blocks, earth mortars etc.) In section 5.4.1 of this report a review of all available national regulation (normative or standards) is given. However, at EU level there is not yet any kind of regulation or code related to construction with such materials even though several EU countries have at least one on their national set of regulations or standards.

Even though constructions with earth materials cannot be generally massive, small constructions of not only residential type are feasible without compromising any crucial issues like safety, stability and energy performance. Numerous of modern earth materials buildings all around Europe prove their feasibility. The major barriers for the broaden adoption of such constructions are: seismic behavior especially in specific countries of seismic areas, susceptible to water damage and the lack of building codes itself. Based on the latest amendments of various EU regulations promoting more sustainable constructions using local resources, recyclable or reusable materials with low embodied carbon emissions it could be the right moment for an EU construction code for earth-based materials. This would encourage the numerous existing initiatives that deal with such constructions and would lift the obstacles for even more to adopt, construct use and live in buildings made from earth-based materials

5 National Regulations of demonstration countries

In this chapter, all the national regulations of the involved countries with a demonstrator building are reviewed. Some regulation or standards categories additional to the EU ones have been added and may apply. These are:

- Urban planning and architecture regulations and issuing building permit
- Anti-Seismic regulation
- RES regulatory framework (e.g. for PV net-metering/net-billing)

Before the regulations, a brief description of the demonstration building(s) is given for each country, based on the up to date available data of the design. Finally, after the regulations there one more section about any possible regulation compliance challenges that have been already identified and need to be highlighted for special attention.

5.1 Germany

5.1.1 Basic characteristics of demonstration buildings

5.1.1.1 Description of DC#1

Demo Building #1 is a new Museum-Pavilion on Campus of TU. As a living lab for planning and building within planetary boundaries, it defines a future-oriented concept for the conception and construction of a sophisticated supporting structure made of reclaimed wood, a foundation made of recycled materials and a low-tech approach. The building site is located in the center of the university's' Campus City West (UCCW), just south of the main building. The proposed design emphasizes ecological ZeB construction, as well as to the surrounding environment with emphasis to the preservation of existing trees. The new building will be used as a museum – exhibition center – and knowledge hub. The eco-friendly design solutions of the building as a contribution to reach ZeB status will be visible for visitors and part of future exhibitions, conferences, seminars, knowledge days for professionals, students and visitors.

1. Type of building use, number of users (permanent staff and visitors): Public building, knowledge hub and exhibition & event space for TU Berlin, expected visitors per year: 20.000-25.000 mostly students, academics and tourists.
2. Size, shape, architectural: The museum pavilion has a rectangular basic shape of 12 x 40 metres and covers a gross floor area of 1200 m² on the 2-3 storeys. In addition to the large and high exhibition halls on the west side of the building and upper floors, the functional areas with lower ceiling heights are located to the east.
3. Building envelope and Materials: The building will be constructed entirely from recycled or sustainable, renewable materials. The building is designed as a complete timber construction with a supporting structure optimised for the use of reclaimed timber (SP2). All load-bearing components -

frames, columns and ceilings (SP3) - are made of wood, as are the exterior walls with an outer façade made of wood. In front of this is a textile façade to protect against the sun and weather. The proportion of glass has been reduced to an appropriate level.

Furthermore, the use of cement and steel is reduced to a necessary minimum - through alternative material selection and structural solutions. An activated clay screed (SP 3) is used as the floor, and a flying foundation is also developed. The house is elevated, the reversible point foundations are optimised for the use of broken concrete and implemented with a minimum amount of cement. Thanks to the foundation form, the floor slab can be made of wood and concrete can be completely dispensed with. More specifically and in order:

- Flying Foundations: elevated building with point foundations optimized for the use of recycled material, with minimal use of cement and steel and sealing of soil
 - Load-bearing structure: (waste-wood) timber frame with lattice grid & solid wood columns
 - Ceilings/Slabs: solid WDLT-Slab and Earth Screed/DLT-Slab and wooden flooring/linoleum
 - External walls: timber paneled construction
 - Facade: textile facade with supporting steel structure, timber batting
 - Internal walls: solid timber frame walls
 - Openings: wood-aluminum triple sun-protection glazed windows, timber doors
 - Roof: solid timber slab (flat roof), intensive green roof on substrate, water retention box
 - Roof & wall insulation: KARZ/wood fibre insulation
4. Technical Systems (heating – cooling – ventilation DHW) and RES: The museum is designed as a low-tech building that almost completely dispenses with the use of building technology. Instead of a technical ventilation system, the building is naturally ventilated, thus challenging the high technical standards for this type of building. Therefore, all rooms have a direct connection to the façade and can therefore be ventilated naturally. Heating is provided by geothermal energy while a cooling system will not be installed. The building's reduced energy requirements are covered by renewable, sustainable energy sources – via PV systems on the roof. (SP14 & 15)
5. GreeNest SPs: SP1, SP2, SP3, SP4, SP5, SP6, SP7, SP14, SP15, SP16

5.1.1.2 Description of DC#2

DC#2 is a new student housing project. HOWOGE aims to make a high-quality and sustainable contribution to the creation of urgently needed affordable housing in Berlin. One floor of the building will be part of GreeNest project.

1. Type of building use: The building operates as a student residence.
2. Size, shape, architectural: The planning of the building has not yet been finalised. The plan is to construct small apartments for students in a timber hybrid design (modular or elemental timber system construction).

3. Building envelope and Materials: The EcoTechWall panels (SP11) will be part of the façade of the HOWOGE’s residential building.
4. Technical Systems (heating – cooling – ventilation DHW) and RES: The part of the building that will be part of the project will be fed by the central heating system.
5. GreeNest SPs: SP2, SP3, SP4, SP5, SP7, SP11, SP16

5.1.2 National regulations

5.1.2.1 Urban Planning / Building construction works / Architecture

Country	Germany
Category	Urban planning – Building construction works - Architecture / Accessibility, safety and hygiene
Regulation Original Title	Bauordnung für Berlin (BauO Bln)
English translation of title	Building Code for Berlin
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2005 / 2023 (latest amendment)
Document type & Status	Type: Regulation or code with legal status Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Berlin
Brief summary / content description	<p>The Building Code for Berlin specifies regulations for buildings in the Federal State of Berlin. Its structure is based on the national Model Building Code and comprises six chapters, each of which is divided into different sections.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. General rules: scope, notions and definitions 2. Land development: construction of buildings, access routes, minimum distances, partitions of plots 3. Built structures: design, construction works and safety requirements, building technologies and building products, fire protection of buildings and building elements, escape routes, technical building services, usage-specific requirements including Design for All 4. Involved parties: basic and individual duties 5. Building authorities and procedures: building permits and related processes 6. Legal provisions: administrative offences, introduction of administrative provisions / technical building rules, processing of personal data, legal proceedings
Scope of: (cases that is applied)	The Building Code applies to all new buildings and to alterations of existing buildings.

<p>Basic requirements for new buildings.</p>	<p>The Building Code describes various requirements for new buildings. New buildings have to be safe regarding structural stability, thermal qualities and fire and sound protection and need to provide appropriate accessibility for various users. Furthermore, the chosen building technologies and building products have to meet current standards and therefore require a usability proof in most cases. Especially regarding fire protection, detailed regulations are described, for instance on permissible material types in terms of fire behavior for different building elements. Many of the requirements mentioned in the Building Code, just like those for fire safety, are further defined and complemented by other regulatory frameworks.</p>
--	--

Country	Germany
Category	Urban planning – Building construction works - Architecture / Accessibility, safety and hygiene
Regulation Original Title	Verwaltungsvorschrift Technische Baubestimmungen (VV TB Bln)
English translation of title	Administrative Provisions / Technical Building Rules for Berlin
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2018 / 2024 (latest amendment)
Document type & Status	Type: Regulation or code with legal status Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Berlin
Brief summary / content description	<p>The Administrative Provisions / Technical Building Rules for Berlin are introduced by and issued on the basis of the Building Code for Berlin. The provisions' structure is based on the national Model Administrative Provisions and consists of parts A to D.</p> <p>Part A describes the applicable technical building rules and standards that need to be followed when fulfilling the basic requirements for buildings, comprising structural stability, fire protection, hygiene / health / environment, safety and accessibility for users, sound and thermal protection.</p> <p>Part B deals with technical building rules for building elements and special constructions, that must be followed additionally to Part A.</p> <p>Part C provides technical rules for building products not certified by a CE-mark and for building technologies, both requiring a usability proof.</p> <p>In Part D, building products are listed, that explicitly do not require a usability proof.</p>
Scope of: (cases that is applied)	The Administrative Provisions / Technical Rules apply to all new buildings and to alterations of existing buildings.

<p>Basic requirements for new buildings.</p>	<p>As the Administrative Provisions / Technical Rules the present a comprehensive listing of compulsory standards for different thematic fields. Buildings have to comply with these. However, the document itself does not feature the actual content, it primarily points to regulations and standards (for instance DIN standards) that need to be applied. It also describes that the use of most building products or technologies require a usability proof.</p>
--	--

5.1.2.2 Structural

Country	Germany
Category	Structural
Regulation Original Title	Eurocode 5: Bemessung und Konstruktion von Holzbauten – Teil 1-1: Allgemeines – Allgemeine Regeln und Regeln für den Hochbau
English translation of title	Eurocode 5: Design of timber structures – Part 1-1: General – Common rules and rules for buildings
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	German version: 2004 2006 (AC) 2008 (A1: last amendment)
Document type & Status	Type: Code with legal status Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	German Version of European Norm
Brief summary / content description	Eurocodes define Europe-wide standardised design rules in the construction industry. Individual National Annexes (NA) are adapted to the circumstances of the nationally defined parameters of the respective member country and apply only in conjunction with the main standard. Eurocode 5 - EN 1995 – applies to the design and construction of buildings and civil engineering works made of wood (solid wood, sawn, planed or as round timber, glued laminated timber or other construction products made of wood for load-bearing purposes, such as laminated veneer lumber) or wood-based materials joined together with adhesives or mechanical fasteners. It fulfills the principles and requirements of EN 1990:2002 for the safety and serviceability of structures and the design and verification procedures.
Scope of: (cases that is applied)	The regulation is applied to all areas of the design and construction of buildings and civil engineering structures made of wood (see list above) or wood-based materials joined together with adhesives or mechanical fasteners. The German version of the Eurocode 5 is applied to new wood-components and wood elements used in construction projects.

<p>Basic requirements for new timber structures.</p>	<p>According to Eurocode 5, the design and construction of timber structures must fulfil the principles and requirements of EN 1990:2002 for the safety and serviceability of structures and the design and verification methods. It defines the requirements for the load-bearing capacity, serviceability, durability and fire resistance of timber structures. Other requirements, for example with regard to thermal and sound insulation, are not covered within this code.</p>
--	--

Country	Germany
Category	Structural
Regulation Original Title	<p>Sortierung von Holz nach der Tragfähigkeit – Teil 1: Nadelholz Teil 2: Baurundholz (Nadelholz) Teil 3: Apparate zur Unterstützung der visuellen Sortierung von Schnittholz; Anforderungen und Prüfung Teil 4: Nachweis der Eignung zur apparativ unterstützten Schnittholzsortierung Teil 5: Laubholz</p>
English translation of title	<p>DIN 4074-1/2/3/4/5 Strength grading of wood Part 1: Coniferous sawn timber Part 2: Structural round timber (Coniferous species) Part 3: Devices for supporting visual grading of sawn timber; Requirements and testing Part 4: Certificate of suitability for devices supporting visual grading of sawn timber Part 5: Sawn hard wood</p>
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2008
Document type & Status	<p>Type: Professional standards (mandatory) Status: Approved and in force</p>
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Germany (when introduced by Administrative Provisions / Technical Building Rules issued by the Federal State)

<p>Brief summary / content description</p>	<p>DIN 4074 regulates the strength grading of construction timber according to load-bearing capacity. Since its last amendment it consists of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Part 1: Coniferous sawn timber Part 2: Structural round timber (Coniferous species) Part 3: Devices for supporting visual grading of sawn timber; Requirements and testing Part 4: Certificate of suitability for devices supporting visual grading of sawn timber Part 5: Sawn hard wood <p>DIN 4074 1, 2, 5 specify grading characteristics and classes as a prerequisite for the determination and application of calculation values for the verification of the limit states of load-bearing capacity and serviceability of Coniferous sawn timber (Part 1), Structural round timber (Coniferous species) (Part 2) and Sawn hard wood (Part 5) according to e.g. DIN EN 1995-1-1 or DIN 1052.</p> <p>DIN 4074 Part 3 specifies how the suitability of the equipment for visually assisted sorting of sawn timber is to be verified. The purpose of this verification is to ensure that companies that visually sort sawn timber in accordance with DIN 4074-1 and DIN 4074-5 have the required suitability.</p> <p>DIN 4074 Part 4 specifies requirements and tests for devices to support the visual grading of sawn timber in accordance with DIN 4074-1 and DIN 4074-5.</p>
<p>Scope of: (cases that is applied)</p>	<p>This standard applies to softwood sawn timber for structural components, for structural round timber (softwood), for hardwood sawn timber for structural components that are to be dimensioned according to load-bearing capacity. It specifies grading characteristics and classes as a prerequisite for the definition and application of calculation values for the verification of the limit states of load-bearing capacity and serviceability according to e.g. DIN EN 1995-1-1 or DIN 1052.</p> <p>Two methods can be used for sorting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - visually (according to section 6); - visually with instrumental support (in accordance with Section 7). <p>This standard fulfils the minimum requirements of DIN EN 14081-1.</p>
<p>Basic requirements for buildings</p>	<p>The sorting of wood according to load-bearing capacity must be carried out in accordance with DIN 4074 on the basis of various sorting characteristics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - knots - fibre inclination

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pith - annual ring width - cracks - Tree edge - curvature - Discolouration, rot - compression wood - Insect damage - Other sorting characteristics - Wood moisture content <p>Visual grading in accordance with DIN 4074 may only be carried out by a trained specialist. A distinction is made between three classes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sawn timber class S7 - Sawn timber class S10 - Sawn timber class S13 <p>Grading with the aid of devices may only be carried out by suitable operators and with equipment tested in accordance with DIN 4074-3.</p> <p>Sorting into the following sorting classes is possible:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sawn timber class S15 <p>The following information is required in the designation: type of sawn timber - DIN 4074 - grading class - dry graded (if applicable) - type of wood.</p>
--	--

Country	Germany
Category	Structural
Regulation Original Title	Bauholz für tragende Zwecke – Festigkeitsklassen; Deutsche Fassung EN 338:2016
English translation of title	Structural timber – Strength classes; German version EN 338:2016
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2016
Document type & Status	Type: Professional standards (mandatory) Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	German version of European Standard 338

<p>Brief summary / content description</p>	<p>This German Version of the European Standard 338 specifies a system of strength classes for general use in design standards. It specifies characteristic values of strength, stiffness and density for each class to which EN 14081-1 refers.</p> <p>In a system of strength classes, grades, species and origins with similar strength properties are grouped into classes within which interchangeability is ensured. This allows the engineer to define a specific strength class and use the characteristic strength values of this class as the basis for his structural calculations.</p>
<p>Scope of: (cases that is applied)</p>	<p>This standard applies to all softwoods and hardwoods for load-bearing purposes in the building sector and new buildings within the scope of EN 14081-1.</p>
<p>Basic requirements for buildings</p>	<p>Basic requirements set by the regulation:</p> <p>For use in construction, solid wood must be strength graded using a visual or mechanical grading process in accordance with EN 14081-1. Different strength classes apply; these are defined in EN 338.</p> <p>The defined strength classes for softwoods and hardwoods as structural timber with a load-bearing function allow a standardisation of engineering calculations. The strength classes are determined on the basis of upright bending tests (table 1) or tensile tests (table 2).</p>

Country	Germany
Category	Structural
Regulation Original Title	Holzbauwerke – Nach Festigkeit sortiertes Bauholz für tragende Zwecke mit rechteckigem Querschnitt – Teil 1: Allgemeine Anforderungen; Deutsche Fassung EN 14081-1:2016+A1:2019
English translation of title	Timber structures – Strength graded structural timber with rectangular cross section – Part 1: General requirements. German version EN 14081-1:2016+A1:2019
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2016 2019 (A1: last amendment)
Document type & Status	Type: Professional standards (mandatory) Status: Approved and in force

Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	German Version of EN 14081-1
Brief summary / content description	<p>This German Version of EN 14081 specifies requirements for visually or mechanically strength graded structural timber of rectangular cross-section produced by sawing, planing or other methods and having cross-sectional dimensions in accordance with EN 338 (hereinafter referred to as 'structural timber').</p> <p>Within this European Standard testing methods, assessment and verification of constancy of performance and marking of structural timber are specified as well as grading characteristics for which limit values shall be given in the standards for visual grading.</p>
Scope of: (cases that is applied)	<p>The German Version of the EN 14081-1 applies to structural timber to be used for construction purposes in Germany, that is either untreated or treated against biological attack.</p> <p>This European Standard does not apply to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - structural timber that has been treated with fire retardants to improve its behaviour when exposed to fire; - thermally and/or chemically modified structural timber; - finger-jointed structural timber for load-bearing purposes.
Basic requirements for buildings	<p>Basic requirements set by the regulation:</p> <p>The requirements for structural timber are defined as follows: Structural timber for load-bearing purposes must be visually or mechanically graded and have characteristic values for bending, tensile, compressive and shear strength, modulus of elasticity and bulk density.</p> <p>It must be assigned to a strength class in accordance with EN 338.</p>

Country	Germany
Category	Structural
Regulation Original Title	Holzbauwerke – Bauholz für tragende Zwecke und Brettschichtholz – Bestimmung einiger physikalischer und mechanischer Eigenschaften; Deutsche Fassung EN 408:2010+A1:2012
English translation of title	Timber structures – Structural timber and glued laminated timber – Determination of some physical and mechanical properties; German version EN 408:2010+A1:2012
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2010 2012 (A1: last amendment)

<p>Document type & Status</p>	<p>Type: Professional standards (mandatory) Status: Approved and in force</p>
<p>Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)</p>	<p>German Version of EN 408</p>
<p>Brief summary / content description</p>	<p>The German Version of European Standard 408 specifies new test methods for the determination of the following properties of structural timber and glued laminated timber: modulus of elasticity in bending, modulus of shear, bending strength, modulus of elasticity in tension in grain direction, tensile strength in grain direction, modulus of elasticity in compression in grain direction, compressive strength in grain direction, modulus of elasticity in tension at right angles to grain direction, tensile strength at right angles to grain direction, modulus of elasticity in compression at right angles to grain direction, compressive strength at right angles to grain direction and shear strength. In addition, the determination of the dimensions, the wood moisture content and the bulk density is specified.</p>
<p>Scope of: (cases that is applied)</p>	<p>Unless otherwise stated, the methods apply to rectangular and circular shapes (with an essentially constant cross-section) made of unjointed or finger-jointed structural timber and glued laminated timber.</p> <p>EN 408 is applicable for suitable timber elements and components in new and old buildings.</p>
<p>Basic requirements for buildings</p>	<p>Basic requirements set by the regulation:</p> <p>EN 408 specifies how some physical and mechanical properties of structural timber and glued laminated timber can be determined. It applies to the following test methods:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Determination of the dimensions of the test specimens – Determination of the moisture content of the test specimens – Determination of the bulk density of the test specimens – Air conditioning of the test specimens – Determination of the local bending modulus of elasticity – Determination of the global modulus of elasticity in bending – Determination of the shear modulus – Determination of the tensile modulus of elasticity in the fiber direction – Determination of the tensile strength in fiber direction – Determination of the compressive modulus of elasticity in the fiber direction – Determination of the compressive strength in the fiber direction – Determination of tensile and compressive strength perpendicular to the fiber direction

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Determination of the modulus of elasticity perpendicular to the fiber direction – Determination of shear strength in fiber direction – Determination of bending strength in fiber direction – Test report <p>This is necessary for the use of corresponding components in new buildings.</p>
--	---

5.1.2.3 Fire Safety

Country	Germany
Category	Fire safety
Regulation Original Title	Muster-Richtlinie über brandschutztechnische Anforderungen an Bauteile und Außenwandbekleidungen in Holzbauweise (MHolzBauRL)
English translation of title	Model-Guideline for fire protection requirements in timber construction
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2020 / 2021 (latest amendment)
Document type & Status	Type: Professional standard (mandatory) Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Germany (if introduced by Administrative Provisions / Technical Building Rules issued by the Federal State)
Brief summary / content description	The MHolzBauRL is one of the Guidelines the Technical Building Rules (VV TB Bln) refer to as standard for fire safety in timber construction. It was introduced in 2020 in order to regulate fire-resistant building elements in solid timber construction and in timber frame construction and their joints. It also sets requirements for exterior claddings made from wood and for horizontal fire barriers.
Scope of: (cases that is applied)	The MHolzBauRL mainly applies to new buildings, especially in building class 4 and 5.
Basic requirements for new buildings.	Some basic requirements from the MHolzBauRL include the following: Highly fire-resistant building elements from combustible materials are permitted only in combination with fire-protective layer from non-combustible materials. Insulation materials have to be non-combustible. The use of combustible insulation materials (like straw or wood fibre) is not covered by the regulation and therefore requires a separate usability proof.

	<p>Exterior claddings from wood or wooden materials are permitted only in combination with a non-combustible board $d \geq 15\text{mm}$ on the outside of the wall.</p> <p>Horizontal fire barriers have to be placed at the height of the ceiling in every story.</p> <p>Adjacent to fire walls, vertical fire barriers are needed. The practical solution for such a vertical barrier is an area of the wall with a width of 1m made of non-combustible materials.</p>
--	---

Country	Germany
Category	Fire safety
Regulation Original Title	DIN 4102-1/2/3/4: Brandverhalten von Baustoffen und Bauteilen
English translation of title	DIN 4102-1/2/4: Fire behaviour of building materials
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	1998, 1977, 1977, 1994 / - - - 2016
Document type & Status	Type: Professional standards (mandatory) Status: Approved and in force The German DIN currently coexists with EN 13051 and will eventually be replaced by the European standard.
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Germany
Brief summary / content description	<p>The DIN 4102 is a technical rule consisting of different parts, all of which describe the fire behavior of building materials and building components, focusing on different aspects.</p> <p>DIN 4102-1 provides regulations on building materials; including definitions, requirements and tests. It introduces the classes A1 / non-combustible materials and A2 / near non-combustible materials with low rates of combustible components; and classes B1-3 / combustible materials, subdivided according to their flammability.</p> <p>DIN 4102-2 covers building components; providing definitions, requirements and tests. It defines fire-resistance classes F30, F60 and F90, describing the approximate number of minutes the component resists to fire. It also links these classes to the specifications made in the Building Codes.</p> <p>DIN 4102-3 refers to fire walls and non-load-bearing external walls; including definitions, requirements and tests.</p>

	DIN 4102-4 describes a synopsis of classified building materials, components and special components and their application, including for example fire resistance classified wood components. For walls, it distinguishes between load-bearing and non-load-bearing and space-enclosing and non-space-enclosing walls. It also rates timber connections according to Eurocode 5 + NA / DIN EN 1995-1-1 with regard to fire resistance classes.
Scope of: (cases that is applied)	DIN 4102 is applicable for new and existing buildings.
Basic requirements for new buildings.	The different parts of DIN 4102 set the framework or “glossary” for fire safety. Rather than requirements for buildings themselves, qualities are defined that other regulations refer to, for examples the Building Code or the MHolzBauRL on fire safety for timber constructions.

Country	Germany / EU
Category	Fire safety
Regulation Original Title	DIN EN 13501-1/2: Klassifizierung von Bauprodukten und Bauarten zu ihrem Brandverhalten; Deutsche Fassung
English translation of title	DIN EN 13051-1/2: Fire classification of construction products and building elements; German version
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2010 / 2016 2019 / 2023
Document type & Status	Type: Professional standards (mandatory) Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	EU / German version
Brief summary / content description	<p>EN 13501-1 provides a classification using data from reaction to fire tests. It differentiates 7 material classes (A1, A2, B, C, D, E, F) and also classifies the emergence of smoke (s1, s2, s3) and the occurrence of flaming droplets/particles (d0, d1, d2) and introduces specific classifications for floorings (fl).</p> <p>EN 13501-2 describes a classification system using data from fire resistance and/or smoke control tests (excluding ventilation services). It defines performance criteria, amongst others stability (R), space enclosure (E), insulation (I), radiation (W), fire protection function (K). Fire resistance is indicated in values ranging from 15 to 360 minutes.</p>
Scope of: (cases that is applied)	DIN EN 13051 is applicable for new buildings and for construction measures in existing buildings.

<p>Basic requirements for new buildings.</p>	<p>DIN EN 13051 sets a framework of classifications for fire safety requirements. allowing comparability via standardised definitions and assessment methods. Rather than requirements for buildings themselves, it defines qualities that other regulations refer to. For example, the Building Code of Berlin defines that non-load bearing external walls must be constructed from non-combustible materials, or the entire enclosing wall must be classified fire-retardant, withstanding fire for 30 minutes. Another example are floor slabs/ceilings, which also have to be capable of resisting to fire for 30 minutes, looking at building class 2 and 3. All these requirements regarding material classes and fire resistance are further defined in DIN EN 13051 and additionally in the German DIN 4102, which is also still in force.</p>
--	---

5.1.2.4 Protection against noise

Country	Germany
Category	Protection against noise - acoustics
Regulation Original Title	DIN 4109: Schallschutz im Hochbau DIN 4109-1: Teil 1: Mindestanforderungen
English translation of title	DIN 4109: Sound insulation in buildings DIN 4109-1: Part 1: Minimum requirements
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	1944 / 2018 (latest amendment)
Document type & Status	Type: Professional standard (mandatory) Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Germany
Brief summary / content description	<p>DIN 4109 is dedicated to noise protection and provides guidelines regarding sound insulation in buildings and assessment methods.</p> <p>DIN 4109-1 in particular defines minimum requirements that have to be met. To ensure noise protection between different units within buildings, minimum insulation values (dB) for different building elements are listed in tables, referring to airborne sound and to impact/footfall sound. The values depend on the use case; requirements vary for apartment buildings, office and mixed-use buildings, for terraced houses, for hotels, for hospitals and for educational buildings. Special requirements regarding dB-values are pointed out for sound insulation between rooms needing particular protection and rooms with increased noise emissions. Emissions from technical installations also have to be taken into account.</p>

	<p>Furthermore, there are provisions for insulation from external sound, applying to enclosing/exterior building elements, depending on the level of noise exposure. The required weighted sound reduction for enclosing elements is calculated subtracting from the specific external noise level a correction value, which depends on the use case.</p> <p>Other parts of the DIN provide guidelines on acoustic assessments and the calculatory proof of sufficient sound insulation in buildings, including data on different construction techniques as base for calculations.</p>
<p>Scope of: (cases that is applied)</p>	<p>DIN 4109 applies to all new buildings and to existing buildings that are significantly altered.</p>
<p>Basic requirements for new buildings.</p>	<p>DIN 4109 names specific values for all kinds of use cases and therefore, basic requirements for new buildings can be listed in an exemplary manner only.</p> <p>Insulation between units within buildings: For example, floor slabs between independent work spaces or similar functions must reach insulation of airborne sound of at least 54dB and insulation of impact sound of at least 53dB.</p> <p>Insulation from external noise: For enclosing facade elements in rooms with residential use, for instance, the required weighted sound reduction value must be at least 30dB, regardless of the external noise, but calculation can also lead to higher values depending on the external noise level.</p>

5.1.2.5 Energy Performance

Country	Germany
Category	Energy performance
Regulation Original Title	Gesetz zur Einsparung von Energie und zur Nutzung erneuerbarer Energien zur Wärme- und Kälteerzeugung in Gebäuden (Gebäudenenergiegesetz, GEG)
English translation of title	Buildings Energy Act
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2020 / 2024
Document type & Status	Type: Law Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Germany
Brief summary / content description	The GEG outlines quality standards for buildings in terms of energy; it regulates their certification and fosters the use of renewable energies for heating systems within buildings. The latest amendment provides binding regulations regarding the energy source of newly installed heating systems.
Scope of: (cases that is applied)	The GEG is applicable for new buildings and for construction measures in existing buildings.
Definition of ZeB / nZeB-standard	The GEG incorporates the concept of nZeBs according to the European Directive on the Energy Performance of Buildings 2018/844/EU (EPBD 3) as a mandatory standard. However, there is no reference to ZeBs within the GEG, but the concept aligns with the overall aim of reducing energy consumption in the building sector as far as possible.
Basic requirements for new buildings.	<p>New buildings have to comply with the nZeB standard, meaning in simplified terms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the total energy required for heating, cooling, ventilation and lighting must not exceed the value of the primary energy demand of a reference building multiplied by the factor of 0.55. - energy losses have to be reduced via thermal insulation to predetermined values (for residential buildings related to a reference building). - heating systems can only be installed if at least 65% of the heat produced by it is generated by the use of renewable energies. <p>Envelope requirements are set with the average thermal transmittance of the building shell. For example, external walls of the reference building are listed with a U-value of 0.28 W/(m²·K). To comply with the GEG, which sets nZeB as minimum standard, this value has to be factored by 0.55, leading</p>

	to a U-value of around 0.15 W/(m ² ·K). However, this single elements value only serves as a rough estimation, as it is not the absolute values that must be complied with, but the averaged heat losses by transmittance, which also take into account the elements surface and position and thermal bridges.
--	---

Country	Germany
Category	Energy performance
Regulation Original Title	DIN 4108-2/3/4/7: Wärmeschutz und Energie-Einsparung in Gebäuden
English translation of title	DIN 4108-2/3/4/7: Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2003 / 2001 / 2004 / 1996 / 2004 2013 / 2024 / 2020 / 2011 / 2021
Document type & Status	Type: Professional standard (mandatory) Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Germany
Brief summary / content description	<p>DIN 4108 outlines requirements regarding thermal protection. Similar to the GEG, its aims at enhanced energy efficiency, indoor comfort and moisture control, providing a set of rules and values that the GEG refers to.</p> <p>DIN 4108-2 sets minimum requirements to thermal insulation. After giving a basic overview on principles of thermal protection, it introduces minimum values of heat transfer resistance for enclosing building elements. Furthermore, it sets minimum requirements on thermal protection in summer, taking into account the applicable summer climate region of the specific object. Thermal bridges are mentioned as well, but further described in supplement 2 containing exemplary designs.</p> <p>DIN 4108-3 is dedicated to the protection against moisture subject to climate conditions - providing requirements, calculation methods and directions for planning and construction. This part aims to avoid damages caused by condensating moisture, especially in winter, and driving rain, but also by summer condensation and reverse-diffusion. It provides definitions and specific variables and their units related to water vapour diffusion, as well as critical values of humidity and guidelines on how to avoid them. To take appropriate measures against driving rain, it outlines groups of exposure to driving rain depending on the region within Germany.</p>

	<p>DIN 4108-4 provides hygrothermal design values, starting with rated values on thermal conductivity and on the water vapour resistance coefficient for different materials. For glazings, windows, doors, curtain walls and skylights, it defines separate values based on the thermal transmission coefficient U, overall energy transmittance g, and the light transmittance T. It also provides a guideline on the required thickness of insulation for pipings.</p> <p>DIN 4108-7 covers the topic of air tightness of buildings, defining requirements, recommendations and examples for planning and performance. The requirements regarding air tightness are based on maximum permissible air exchange rates for buildings with and without ventilation systems. Recommendations and examples provide guidelines on how a high level of air tightness can be achieved.</p> <p>DIN 4108-10 outlines application-specific requirements for insulating materials, providing separate tables for different materials.</p>
Scope of: (cases that is applied)	DIN 4108 is applicable for new buildings and for substantial changes in existing buildings.
Basic requirements for new buildings.	New buildings have to be built in a way that thermal transmission is limited to a very low level and overheating in summer is prevented. They have to be safe from driving rain and need to reach a high level of air tightness. Thermal bridges have to be avoided through careful design and construction of the building.

5.1.2.6 Sustainable use of natural resources

Country	Germany
Category	Sustainable use of natural resources
Regulation Original Title	Gesetz zur Förderung der Kreislaufwirtschaft und Sicherung der umweltverträglichen Bewirtschaftung von Abfällen (Kreislaufwirtschaftsgesetz - KrWG)
English translation of title	Act on the Promotion of the Circular Economy and Ensuring the Environmentally Sound Management of Waste (Circular Economy Act)
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2012 2023 (last amendment)
Document type & Status	Type: Law/regulation Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Germany

<p>Brief summary / content description</p>	<p>The purpose of the Act on the Promotion of the Circular Economy and Ensuring the Environmentally Sound Management of Waste is to promote circular economy in order to conserve natural resources and to ensure the protection of people and the environment in the generation and management of waste.</p> <p>This Act is also intended to ensure that the European targets set out in Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives are met.</p>
<p>Scope of: (cases that is applied)</p>	<p>For the purposes of this Act, waste is any substance or object which the holder discards, intends to discard or must discard. Waste for recovery is waste that is recovered; waste that is not recovered is waste for disposal.</p> <p>The provisions of this Act shall apply to</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. the prevention of waste and 2. the recovery of waste, 3. the disposal of waste and 4. other waste management measures <p>Prevention and waste management measures are prioritized as follows:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. prevention, 2. preparation for reuse 3. recycling, 4. other recovery, in particular energy recovery and backfilling, 5. disposal. <p>The obligations to prevent waste are governed by § 13 and the ordinances issued on the basis of §§ 24 and 25.</p>
<p>Basic requirements for new buildings.</p>	<p>Basic requirements set by the regulation:</p> <p>The Act on the Promotion of the Circular Economy and Ensuring the Environmentally Sound Management of Waste defines, that the producers or holders of waste are obliged to recycle their waste and that the recovery of waste shall take precedence over its disposal.</p> <p>Condition is, that the recovery of waste, in particular through its incorporation into products, must be carried out properly and without causing harm. Furthermore, the recovery shall be carried out properly and in a harmless manner if the nature of the waste, the extent of the contamination and the type of recovery are not expected to be detrimental to the public good, in particular if there is no accumulation of pollutants in the cycle of recyclable materials.</p> <p>According to the act, the obligation to recover waste must be fulfilled if this is technically possible and economically reasonable, in particular if a market exists or can be created for a recovered substance or recovered</p>

	<p>energy. It is specified, that the recovery of waste is also technically possible if this requires pre-treatment and that economic reasonableness is given if the costs associated with recovery are not disproportionate to the costs that would have to be borne for waste disposal.</p> <p>This regulation applies to waste generated in the construction sector as part of new construction, remodeling or demolition projects.</p>
--	---

Country	GERMANY
Category	Sustainable use of natural resources
Regulation Original Title	Verordnung über Anforderungen an die Verwertung und Beseitigung von Altholz (Altholzverordnung - AltholzV)
English translation of title	Ordinance in requirements for the Recycling and Elimination of waste-wood (AltHolzV)
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2002 2020 (last amendment)
Document type & Status	Type: Federal ordinance Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Germany
Brief summary / content description	<p>The Ordinance on Requirements for the Utilisation and Disposal of waste-wood (AltholzV) regulates the utilisation and disposal of waste-wood in the Federal Republic of Germany. It defines the term waste-wood as industrial waste-wood and used wood, insofar as it is waste according to the definition of the Circular Economy Act (KrWG).</p> <p>Following categories of waste-wood are defined:</p> <p>waste-wood category A I: Natural or merely mechanically processed waste-wood that has not been more than insignificantly contaminated with non-wood substances during its use,</p> <p>waste-wood category A II: Glued, painted, coated, varnished or otherwise treated waste-wood without organohalogen compounds in the coating and without wood preservatives,</p> <p>waste-wood category A III: waste-wood with organohalogen compounds in the coating without wood preservatives,</p>

	<p>waste-wood category A IV: waste-wood treated with wood preservatives, as well as other waste-wood that cannot be assigned to waste-wood categories A I, II or III due to its pollutant load, with the exception of PCB waste-wood;</p> <p>The ordinance differentiates between material and energy utilisation of waste-wood:</p> <p>Material utilisation of waste-wood:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Processing of waste-wood into wood chips and wood shavings for the production of wood-based materials, – Production of synthesis gas for further chemical utilisation and – Production of activated carbon/industrial charcoal; <p>Energy recovery from waste-wood.</p>
Scope of: (cases that is applied)	<p>This Ordinance applies to the recycling, energy recovery and disposal of waste-wood for producers and owners of waste-wood, operators of facilities in which waste-wood is recycled or disposed of, public waste management authorities, insofar as they recycle or dispose of waste-wood and third parties, associations and self-governing bodies of the economy to whom obligations for the recycling or disposal of waste-wood have been transferred in accordance with the Closed Substance Cycle and Waste Management Act of 27 September 1994.</p>
Basic requirements for new buildings.	<p>This ordinance applies to all waste-wood in Germany. If built with waste-wood this applies also to new buildings, new components and elements.</p>

Country	GERMANY / EU
Category	Sustainable use of natural resources
Regulation Original Title	DIN EN 13171: Wärmedämmstoffe für Gebäude - Werkmäßig hergestellte Produkte aus Holzfasern (WF) - Spezifikation; Deutsche Fassung
English translation of title	DIN EN 13171: Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made wood fiber (WF) products - Specification; German version
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2003 / 2015
Document type & Status	Type: Professional standard (mandatory) Status: Approved and in force

Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Germany (EU)
Brief summary / content description	DIN EN 13171 regulates factory-made wood fiber insulation products and defines requirements, properties and test methods. It outlines permissible components and additives and defines basic properties, for instance regarding thermal conductivity, tensile and compressive strength or reaction to fire, providing applicable testing methods. Furthermore, labelling and CE-marking are addressed.
Scope of: (cases that is applied)	DIN EN 13171 applies to factory-made wood fiber insulation products for buildings.
Basic requirements for new buildings.	DIN EN 13171 is the harmonised norm applicable for CE-marking of wood-fibre boards and defines their properties for technical approval. The norm focuses on the material itself more than it's practical application and does not provide application-specific requirements for different use cases. This is covered by DIN 4108-10.

Country	GERMANY
Category	Sustainable use of natural resources
Regulation Original Title	DIN EN 13986: Holzwerkstoffe zur Verwendung im Bauwesen - Eigenschaften, Bewertung der Konformität und Kennzeichnung; Deutsche Fassung
English translation of title	DIN EN 13986: Wood-based panels for use in construction - Characteristics, evaluation of conformity and marking
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2002 / 2015
Document type & Status	Type: Professional standards (mandatory) Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Germany

<p>Brief summary / content description</p>	<p>DIN EN 13986 points out relevant performance criteria for each type of panel, taking into account their application. Some examples are density, moisture resistance, noise insulation, thermal conductivity, formaldehyde emissions or stiffness of the panels. Subsequently, these performance criteria are described, including applicable methods to determine the specific properties referring to each criterion.</p> <p>Furthermore, the regulation addresses the assessment of constancy of performance and outlines requirements for the labelling of the products, introducing different technical classes for all types of panels.</p>
<p>Scope of: (cases that is applied)</p>	<p>DIN EN 13986 applies to wood-based panels for use in construction, like oriented strand boards (OSB), plywood, wood fibre boards and similar products.</p>
<p>Basic requirements for new buildings.</p>	<p>According to DIN EN 13986, wood-based panels have to be safe and durable enough for use in construction and need to be assessed and labelled according to the regulation.</p>

5.1.2.7 Earthen/bio-based/natural materials

In Germany, there are also several standards about earthen material and products that are used for building construction. The most important for Greenest project (based on the type of materials and elements that are going to be used in the demo buildings) are presented below:

Country	GERMANY
<p>Category</p>	<p>Earthen/bio-based/natural materials</p>
<p>Regulation Original Title</p>	<p>DIN 18942-1:2024-03: Lehmbaustoffe und Lehmbauprodukte – Teil 1: Begriffe & Teil 100: Übereinstimmungs- und Konformitätsnachweis</p>
<p>English translation of title</p>	<p>DIN 18942-1:2024-03: Earthen materials and products - Part 1: Vocabulary & Part 100: Conformity assessment</p>
<p>Publication year / amendment year (if any)</p>	<p>2010 / 2024</p>
<p>Document type & Status</p>	<p>Type: Professional standards (mandatory) Status: Approved and in force</p>
<p>Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)</p>	<p>Germany</p>

Brief summary / content description	<p>The standard (Part 1) defines all terms and applications for earth materials according to DIN 18945, DIN 18946, DIN 18947, DIN 18948 and DIN 18940. For each of the earth products definitions of components, terms for testing methods and properties of the raw material and finished product are defined.</p> <p>Part 100 regulates the production control for earth-material-manufacturers. It defines which test protocols have to be determined and in what time interval. It differentiates between the first control and controls which has to be repeated in a defined time interval.</p>
Scope of: (cases that is applied)	As a standard it's applicable for new buildings and for construction measures in existing buildings in Germany as well as for the production of earth materials as building products.
Basic requirements for new buildings.	Earth materials and products have to comply with standards in Germany.

Country	Germany
Category	Earthen/bio-based/natural materials
Regulation Original Title	DIN 18947:2024-03: Lehmputzmörtel – Anforderungen, Prüfung und Kennzeichnung
English translation of title	DIN 18947:2024-03: Earth plasters - Requirements, test and labelling
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2010 / 2024
Document type & Status	Type: Professional standards (mandatory) Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Germany
Brief summary / content description	It defines the construction physical properties of earth-plaster. For example, the minimum compressive strength or bending tensile strength. Also, it regulates the test-methods to determine those values. The standard also gives information on the life cycle assessment and the recycling potential. All possible ingredients are defined.
Scope of: (cases that is applied)	The standard is applicable for new buildings and for construction measures in existing buildings.
Basic requirements for new buildings.	Earth materials and products have to comply with standards in Germany.

Country	Germany
Category	Earthen/bio-based/natural materials
Regulation Original Title	DIN 18948:2024-03: Lehmplatten – Anforderungen, Prüfung und Kennzeichnung
English translation of title	DIN 18948:2024-03: Earthen boards - Requirements, test and labelling
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2010 / 2024
Document type & Status	Type: Professional standards (mandatory) Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Germany
Brief summary / content description	It defines the construction physical properties of earth-boards. For example, the minimum compressive strength or bending tensile strength. Also, it regulates the test-methods to determine those values. The standard also gives information on the life cycle assessment and the recycling potential. All possible ingredients are defined. Earth boards can be applied as panelling or cladding.
Scope of: (cases that is applied)	The standard is applicable for new buildings and for construction measures in existing buildings.
Basic requirements for new buildings.	Earth materials and products have to comply with standards in Germany.

Country	Germany
Category	Earthen/bio-based/natural materials
Regulation Original Title	Lehmbau Regeln: Begriffe – Baustoffe – Bauteile
English translation of title	Earth Building Rules: Terms – Buildings Materials – Components
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	1999 / 2009
Document type & Status	Type: Technical regulation (mandatory) Status: Approved by DIBt (German Technical Institute for Structural Engineering; German: Deutsches Institut für Bautechnik) and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Germany

Brief summary / content description	Guideline on all possible earth-building-techniques. It defines simple test methods to estimate quality of material and product. It describes different construction-methods and allowed ingredients in mixtures. Hygrothermal and physical properties of earth material.
Scope of: (cases that is applied)	As a technical regulation approved by DIBt it is a state-of-the-art guideline for building with earth. Also, all standards by DIN refer to the regulation.
Basic requirements for new buildings.	It completes requirements by DIN.

5.1.2.8 RES regulatory framework

Country	Germany
Category	Renewable energy sources regulatory framework
Regulation Original Title	Erneuerbare-Energien-Gesetz (EEG)
English translation of title	Renewable Energy Sources Act
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2000 / 2023
Document type & Status	Type: Law Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Germany
Brief summary / content description	The Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG) fosters the transition of the German energy sector towards renewable energy sources and regulates the connection and feed-in of renewable energy to the grid, including intermediate milestones. It aims at a sustainable development of the overall energy supply to save fossil resources while ensuring economic and technological reliability and fostering innovation. Therefore, the law sets goals to increase the installed capacity of wind turbines on- and offshore, photovoltaic systems and biomass power plants. Other renewable sources according to the law are hydropower and geothermal energy. Depending on the installed capacity, the EEG determines feed-in tariffs for renewable energies thus providing long-term calculability and reliability regarding the economic feasibility of renewable energy.
Scope of: (cases that is applied)	The EEG applies to the German energy sector.

<p>Basic requirements for new buildings.</p>	<p>Until 2030, 80% of the gross energy consumption need to be covered by energy generated from renewable sources. After conclusion of the coal phase-out (2038), Germany’s energy supply shall reach carbon-neutrality. The installed capacity of solar power must reach 215 GW by 2030. To reach this goal, some of the previous regulations have been adjusted in the latest amendment. For instance, the 70%-cap for energy feed-in of some PV systems no longer applies. The feed-in tariffs are now slightly higher than they have been in previous versions. The EEG continues to support self-consumption of solar energy in combination with storage systems as well as with feed-in solutions for excess energy. PV-Systems up to 30 kW benefit from simplified grid connection processes. The latest amendment also clarifies that storage systems are not to be classified as consumers, so that double grid charges are avoided. If, in contrast, all of the produced energy is fed into the grid, there are other financial incentives, as well as for special models for tenants of multi-unit-buildings. Via adjusted regulations, bypassing the public grid and thus avoiding certain grid usage fees and taxes, tenants can benefit from lower energy prices. Subsidies aim to further promote this model.</p>
--	---

5.1.3 Compliance challenges

As the technical solutions developed within the GreeNest framework will be of innovative nature, challenges regarding their compliance with the above-mentioned provisions must be anticipated.

For DC# 1, the Berlin Museum Pavilion, an increased effort is expected in the implementation of GreeNest materials within the current legal framework in Germany. The construction sector in Germany is primarily geared towards linear value chains, as are the associated and applicable regulations. The reuse of waste-materials as building materials is a non-common practice – in particular in the area of load-bearing structures and components. Therefore, a legally secure concept that complies with current standardisation is necessary, as well as new planning-, production- and construction-processes. (SP2)

The innovative WDLT-Slab (SP3) will have to meet the requirements from the Berlin Building Code and Construction Products Regulations. Timber elements, such as the WDLT-slab, usually require CE marking. If timber components are to be reinstalled at another location as load-bearing components, the timber must be categorised in a strength class in accordance with DIN EN 408. When using fresh timber, such a declaration of performance and, under certain circumstances, CE marking is carried out by the manufacturing company. CE marking of waste-wood by the manufacturer is not currently planned or regulated. To achieve this, the first step will be to legally prevent the material from becoming waste in order to avoid it falling into the complex area of waste legislation and regulations. As for the other German Demo Building and EcoTechWall, part of the further research will be the development of a concept and process for the implementation of waste-wood within the current certification framework.

Early coordination with the bench test engineer responsible for the construction project is of fundamental importance. It is to be expected that individual authorization will have to be found for the initial implementation of the innovative approaches within the demo buildings. The aim of the GreenNest project is to derive recommendations for the adaptation of regulations and standards.

As described above, compliance with current regulations poses significant challenges to the realisation of the SPs within DC1, this applies in particular to certification of waste-wood and the product development of waste-wood.

For DC2, the Berlin Lodge, it is expected that considerable effort will be required to achieve an innovative yet technically and legally feasible solution. This applies in particular to the EcoTechWall.

The innovative wall element must meet the requirements from the Berlin Building Code and the Technical Building Rules. Among other aspects, these regulations determine which products can be used for construction. Timber, for example, is covered by harmonised standards (hEN) and therefore normally requires CE marking according to the Construction Products Regulations. Further research will be carried out to determine how the use of reclaimed wood in the EcoTechWall could fit into this certification framework, or whether alternative options might prove more suitable for achieving compliance.

In terms of fire safety, the Berlin Building Code and the Technical Building Rules like the MHolzBauRL define the qualities of the integrated materials and the fire resistance of the wall as a whole. However, complying with all the rules would mean compromising on innovation - to give an example, natural insulation materials would be excluded, as they are normally flammable. In common building practice, such a deviation from technical rules is often overcome by referring to an existing test certificate as proof of usability. In the case of the insulation, there are certified wall constructions using wood-based insulation materials, that have been proven to have a certain level of fire resistance.

In order to realise innovations going beyond existing test certificates, such as the integration of non-certified reuse-wood or the replacement or reduction of layers and materials within the wall, other ways of achieving compliance can be explored. Deviating components could be legitimised by obtaining a proof of equivalence. Individual technical approval can be sought for a particular technical solution to be implemented in a specific building project. However, there are other challenges associated with these options, like the time and resources required for such an approach.

As described, compliance with current regulations poses significant challenges to the realisation of DC2. This applies in particular to certification and fire safety requirements of the EcoTechWall, which will potentially include innovations currently not covered by the regulatory framework. The GreenNest project provides an opportunity to address these challenges and identify ways to overcome them.

5.2 Italy

5.2.1 Basic characteristics of demonstration building - DC#3 Delta demo in Porto Viro

1. Type of building use, users: Touristic info-center and a boat warehouse for fishermen.
2. Size, shape, architectural: Single floor, simple rectangular shape and small size of approximately 60 m² with a facade area of 121 m².
3. Building envelope and Materials: The building area will be characterized from reinforced concrete with recycled steel; facade by timber studs and walls with parts of GreenWall (SP10); Load-bearing and bracing interior walls by solid wood construction; Non-load bearing interior walls by lightweight construction; roof similar to floor slabs with ceramic tiles; timber framed triple glazed windows.
4. Technical Systems (heating – cooling – ventilation) and RES: Heat pump for heating and cooling and BIPV for onsite energy generation.
5. GreenNest SPs: SP4, SP5, SP6, SP8, SP9, SP10, SP12, SP13, SP14, SP15, SP16

5.2.2 National regulations

5.2.2.1 Urban Planning / Building construction works / Architecture

Country	Italy
Category	<i>Building construction works</i>
Regulation Original Title	Testo Unico Edilizia (DPR 380/2001)
English translation of title	Consolidated Law on Building (DPR 380/2001)
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2001 – Various amendments are made (2016, 2017, 2019, 2020, 2022, 2023, 2024)
Document type & Status	Decree of the President of the Republic – approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Countrywide

<p>Brief summary / content description</p>	<p>Defines the rules to be followed at national level in construction matters. Since it was issued, the text has undergone a series of changes, sometimes very important and impacting on the professional activity of the technician and, more generally, of all the actors in the construction industry (companies, clients, subcontractors, contracting stations, etc.). The Presidential Decree 380/2001 defines the fundamental provisions in building activities with reference to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • building interventions • licenses and permits • habitability of buildings • supervision of urban-building activities, responsibilities and sanctions • technical building regulations (regulations for reinforced, normal and pre-stressed concrete and metal structure works, limiting energy consumption in buildings, plant safety, construction in seismic areas and architectural barriers)
<p>Scope of: (cases that is applied)</p>	<p>This Consolidated Law on Building contains the fundamental and general principles and provisions for the regulation of building activity.</p>
<p>Basic requirements for new buildings.</p>	<p>-</p>

Country	Italy
<p>Category</p>	<p><i>Landscape Assessment</i></p>
<p>Regulation Original Title</p>	<p>D.P.R. 31/2017 – “Autorizzazione Paesaggistica Semplificata”</p>
<p>English translation of title</p>	<p>D.P.R. 31/2017 – Simplified Landscape Assessment”</p>
<p>Publication year / amendment year (if any)</p>	<p>2017</p>
<p>Document type & Status</p>	<p>Law – Approved and in force</p>
<p>Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)</p>	<p>Countrywide</p>
<p>Brief summary / content description</p>	<p>The landscape authorisation is a prerequisite act with respect to the titles legitimising the urban-building intervention: building permit, authorisation title, etc. It is a mandatory document for all interventions on buildings and areas of landscape interest protected by law. The simplified landscape authorisation refers to the authorisation required for</p>

	<p>interventions of minor importance and landscape impact as set out in Annex B of Presidential Decree 31/2017.</p> <p>Article 8 of Presidential Decree 31/2017 regulates the procedures for filling out the application to obtain the simplified landscape authorisation for minor works and specifies the documentation to be attached. In particular, it is provided that the application must be filled in using the simplified model in Annex C of Presidential Decree 31/2017 and must be accompanied by a simplified landscape report based on Annex D of the same regulation.</p>
Scope of: (cases that is applied)	Mandatory for all interventions on buildings and areas in a landscape of interest and protected by law
Basic requirements for new buildings.	-

5.2.2.2 Structural

Country	Italy
Category	<i>Seismic and Structural</i>
Regulation Original Title	Norme Tecniche per le costruzioni (Decreto 17/01/2018) – NTC 2018
English translation of title	Technical standards for constructions
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2018 – Updated in 2019 (Circular 7/2019 - Update of technical construction standards)
Document type & Status	Decree of the Minister of Infrastructure and Transport – Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Countrywide
Brief summary / content description	<p>These are fundamental regulations as they define the principles to be followed for the design, execution and testing of constructions and specify the performance that buildings must achieve in terms of mechanical resistance and stability.</p> <p>The normative text in fact provides a series of directives concerning the construction, demolition or structural modification of both public and private buildings such as</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - design, execution and testing of constructions;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - types of materials to be used depending on the type of work to be carried out, - performance to be achieved in terms of mechanical resistance and stability; - regulatory and implementation aspects related to the presence of seismic actions; - prescriptions and indications concerning the relationship of the works with the ground and, in general, geotechnical aspects.
<p>Scope of: (cases that is applied)</p>	<p>Public construction works, public utility construction works and private construction works.</p>
<p>Basic requirements for new buildings.</p>	<p>This document provides a detailed regulatory framework to ensure the safety, durability, and structural efficiency of buildings. Below are some of the main requirements established by NTC 2018:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Structural Safety: Structures must be designed and constructed to ensure an adequate level of safety against major risks such as earthquakes, environmental loads, and accidents. NTC 2018 introduces rigorous seismic design criteria, mandatory throughout the national territory. 2. Building Materials: The materials used must meet specific characteristics of strength, durability, and quality. They must comply with European and national regulations, with particular attention to sustainability and environmental impact. 3. Structural Design and Calculation: Design must be carried out by qualified professionals using recognized calculation methods and certified software. Projects must include details on loads, stresses, and safety verifications. 4. Fire Safety Standards: Buildings must be designed to ensure safety in the event of fire, including measures such as the fire resistance of structures, safe escape routes, and alarm and extinguishing systems. 5. Accessibility and Usability: Buildings must be accessible to all people, including those with disabilities, in compliance with current regulations on the accessibility of public and private spaces. 6. Energy Efficiency: NTC 2018 promotes the energy efficiency of buildings, requiring the adoption of design and technical solutions that reduce energy consumption and encourage the use of renewable sources. 7. Documentation and Certifications: Each project must be accompanied by complete documentation including material certifications, structural calculations, maintenance plans, and all necessary authorizations.

5.2.2.3 Fire Safety

5.2.2.4 Energy Performance

Country	Italy
Category	Energy Performance of Buildings
Regulation Original Title	Decreto Legislativo 192/2005 – Prestazione Energetica in Edilizia
English translation of title	Legislative Decree 192/2005 – Energy performance of Buildings
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2005 – amended in 2013
Document type & Status	Law – approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Countrywide
Brief summary / content description	Legislative Decree 192/2005 (implementing Directive 2002/91/EC and amended by Law 90/2013) establishes criteria for improving the energy performance of buildings. In order to ensure an improvement in the energy efficiency of buildings, the decree imposes a series of obligations, non-compliance with which may lead to an administrative penalty up to and including a serious offence in the case of false declarations.
Scope of: (cases that is applied)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • new buildings; • major renovations; • energy requalification; • extensions of more than 15%; • thermal installations; • replacement of heat generators; • demolition and reconstruction.
Basic requirements for new buildings.	-

Country	Italy
Category	Energy Performance of Buildings
Regulation Original Title	Decreto legge 63/2013 - Legge 90/2013 - "Disposizioni urgenti per il recepimento della Direttiva 2010/31/UE del Parlamento europeo e del Consiglio del 19 maggio 2010, sulla prestazione energetica nell'edilizia"

English translation of title	Decree-Law 63/2013 - Law 90/2013 - 'Urgent provisions for the implementation of Directive 2010/31/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings'
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2013
Document type & Status	Law – Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Countrywide
Brief summary / content description	Decree Law 63/2013 of 4 June (Law 90/2013) determines urgent provisions for the implementation of Directive 2010/31/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on energy performance in buildings for the settlement of infringement proceedings initiated by the European Commission, as well as other provisions on social cohesion.
Scope of: (cases that is applied)	Decree Law 63/2013 provides for a series of amendments to various articles of Legislative Decree 192/05 and introduces various provisions on tax deductions for energy efficiency interventions. In particular, it establishes some changes regarding the energy performance certificate (APE), specifying the penalties in the event of failure to draw up the document; it introduces the furniture bonus, determining how much the tax deduction amounts to in reference to the purchase of furniture. Finally, it decrees the so-called seismic bonus, providing for larger deductions and more specific rules to take advantage of tax benefits in the event of seismic events.
Basic requirements for new buildings.	-

Country	Italy
Category	Energy Performance of Buildings
Regulation Original Title	Decreto Ministeriale 26/06/2015 – “Decreto Requisiti Minimi”
English translation of title	Ministerial Decree 26/06/2015 - ‘Minimum Requirements Decree’.
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2015
Document type & Status	Law – Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Countrywide
Brief summary / content description	<p>The Minimum Requirements Decree (Ministerial Decree 26/06/2015) - introduces some amendments to Legislative Decree 192/2005 implementing the European Union's directive on nearly zero energy buildings (Directive 2010/31/EU).</p> <p>- It sets calculation methods and new minimum requirements for the energy performance of buildings, in force on 1 October 2015.</p> <p>The Minimum Requirements Decree introduces the concept of a ‘reference building’, i.e. a building that is identical to the design or real building in terms of geometry, orientation, spatial location, intended use and boundary situation and has predetermined thermal characteristics and energy parameters.</p> <p>According to the new rules, 2 calculations will be required:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - calculation of the energy performance of the reference building; - calculation of the energy performance of the real building, which will be compared with the relevant reference building. <p>The purpose is to have a reference for calculating a set of limits that buildings will have to comply with, depending on whether they are being renovated or upgraded.</p>
Scope of: (cases that is applied)	<p>New buildings</p> <p>Existing building extensions with a volume of more than 15% of the existing building or 500 m³</p> <p>Major renovation of first level</p> <p>Major renovation of second level</p> <p>Energy requalification</p>
Basic requirements for new buildings.	$H'_T < H'_{T,lim}$ $A_{sol,est}/A_{sup,utile} < A_{sol,est}/A_{sup,utile,lim}$ $EP_{gl,tot} < EP_{gl,tot,lim}$ $EP_{H,nd} < EP_{H,nd,lim}$ $EP_{C,nd} < EP_{C,nd,lim}$ $\eta_W > \eta_{W,lim}$

	$\eta_H > \eta_{H,lim}$ $\eta_C > \eta_{C,lim}$ limits calculated with reference building defined in Appendix A
--	---

5.2.3 Compliance challenges

The prefabricated DeltaSmart and the GreenWall are innovative modular building construction methods and there is a possibility that some technical specifications may not be fit the construction regulations of Italy. In addition, due to the high humidity of the area and the existence of salt due to proximity to the sea, might create problems to various materials and components

The demo building at the delta area of Porto Viro is in a very early design stage and the estimation of the energy demand for heating and cooling has not been done yet. According to the GreenNest project and the GA, building integrated PV (BIPV) systems will be the only renewable energy system which is going to be integrated on the roof and on the façade of the building. The possible challenge is if the total PV installed power will be sufficient to generate the amount of energy needed to reach ZeB level given the small roof area.

5.3 Greece

5.3.1 Basic characteristics of demonstration building - DC#4 North Aegean demo

1. Type of building use, users: Museum, cultural and recreation center, used by tourists, students and various professionals.
2. Size, shape, architectural: Polygonal size, single floor with a traditional pitcher roof
3. Building envelope and Materials:
 - Foundations: Reinforced concrete/recycled steel
 - Floors: Timber flooring
 - External walls: Natural stone & Mortar, Concrete Beams
 - External finishing: Natural Stone finishing
 - Internal walls: Masonry (Brick)
 - Openings: Timber framed double glazed windows and timber doors
 - Roof: Single pitch, timber framed roof with ceramic tiles (terracotta)
 - Wall's insulation: SmartWall's insulation material – sheep wool
 - Roof insulation: SmartRoof's insulation material – sheep wool
4. Technical Systems (heating – cooling – ventilation DHW) and RES: Heat pump for heating and cooling with fan coils, BIPV for onsite renewable generation.
5. GreeNest SPs: SP4, SP5, SP6, SP8, SP9, SP13, SP14, SP15, SP16

5.3.2 National regulations

5.3.2.1 Urban Planning / Building construction works / Architecture

Country	Greece
Category	Building construction works - urban planning
Regulation Original Title	ΝΕΟΣ ΟΙΚΟΔΟΜΙΚΟΣ ΚΑΝΟΝΙΣΜΟΣ – ΝΟΚ
English translation of title	NEW BUILDING CONSTRUCTIONS REGULATION
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2012 – with 22 later amendments
Document type & Status	Type: Regulations, codes with legal status Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	The regulation is applied countrywide

Brief summary / content description	<p>The regulation gives the definitions of building related types of constructions and related processes and sets restrictions regarding their size, location etc. while also defines all types of building quantities and factors related with building areas, dimensions, coverage, heights etc. It defines all the building permits and where they are mandatory.</p> <p>It deals with cases of buildings with special architecture, motivation for buildings that reach high energy performance and with access and functional requirements in all buildings for people with disabilities.</p>
Scope of: (All cases that is applied)	The regulation is applied to all urban and non-urban areas for new and existing buildings and infrastructure.

5.3.2.2 Structural

Country	Greece
Category	Seismic behaviour
Regulation Original Title	ΕΛΛΗΝΙΚΟΣ ΑΝΤΙΣΕΙΣΜΙΚΟΣ ΚΑΝΟΝΙΣΜΟΣ – ΕΑΚ
English translation of title	GREEK ANTI-SEISMIC REGULATION
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2000 – (last corrections 2016)
Document type & Status	Type: Regulations, codes with legal status Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	The regulation is applied countrywide
Brief summary / content description	<p>The anti-seismic regulation is the basic tool for design and construction of buildings and infrastructure able to withstand with safety the intense stresses of an earthquake up to specific magnitudes. The basic purpose of the regulation is to protect human life in case of high magnitude earthquakes, mitigation of material and property loss in case of mediocre magnitude and to set a minimum level of requirements for constructions. The 2001 regulation complied with the Eurocode 7 and Eurocode 8.</p>
Scope of: (All cases that is applied)	The regulation is applied to all urban and non-urban areas for new and buildings and other civil works, as well as vertical expansions of existing buildings. The regulation is valid in parallel with other design regulations of specific material (concrete, masonry, steel, wood etc.) that include specified requirements and more detailed rules for sizing in order to withstand seismic action.

Country	Greece
Category	Mechanical resistance, stability and seismic behaviour
Regulation Original Title	ΕΥΡΩΚΩΔΙΚΕΣ 0-9 με ΕΘΝΙΚΑ ΠΡΟΣΑΡΤΗΜΑΤΑ και EN
English translation of title	EUROCODES 0-9 with National Appendices
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2009 – (in 2014 the codes were adopted nationally)
Document type & Status	Type: Codes with legal status Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	The regulation is applied EU wide with some parameters left to be defined nationally.
Brief summary / content description	See section 4.2
Scope of: (All cases that is applied)	Eurocodes with national Appendixes are applied to every building construction as well as other types of works and facilities

Country	Greece
Category	Mechanical resistance, stability and seismic behaviour
Regulation Original Title	Ελληνικός Κανονισμός Οπλισμένου Σκυροδέματος (ΕΚΩΣ) & Κανονισμός Τεχνολογίας Σκυροδέματος (ΚΤΣ)
English translation of title	Greek Regulation of Reinforced Concrete & Regulation of Concrete Technology
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2000 – (latest ammendment 2010)
Document type & Status	Type: Regulation with legal status Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	The regulation is applied countrywide and in parallel with the Eurocodes
Brief summary / content description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Greek Regulation of Reinforced Concrete is valid for constructions made of reinforced and/or pre-stressed concrete with usual aggregates as they are defined in the Regulation of Concrete Technology b) Regulation of Concrete Technology specifies the minimum requirements, both general and specific that concrete and works with concrete should comply with. For Eurocodes See section 4.2

Scope of: (All cases that is applied)	The regulations are applied for all construction works where reinforced concrete is used.
---------------------------------------	---

5.3.2.3 Fire safety

Country	Greece
Category	Safety in case of fire in buildings
Regulation Original Title	ΚΑΝΟΝΙΣΜΟΣ ΠΥΡΟΠΡΟΣΤΑΣΙΑΣ ΚΤΗΡΙΩΝ
English translation of title	BUILDING FIRE PROTECTION REGULATION
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2018
Document type & Status	Type: Regulations, codes with legal status Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (if differentiated countrywide)	The regulation is applied countrywide
Brief summary / content description	<p>The regulation defines all the measures and requirements that should be taken in buildings in order to protect the life and health of building users in case of fire, to prevent the spread of fire from one space to other spaces of the same building or other buildings and regions and to protect the buildings themselves and their content. Primary target is the human safety in case of fire by appropriate building design, equipment and material selection and by installing appropriate active fire protection systems. More specifically in the regulation are defined:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the measures that protect a building for collapsing at least for as long as it takes for its evacuation, - the minimum requirements regarding the design of the escape routes for fast and safe evacuation of the users protecting them from smoke, heat and other toxic substances, - the maximum allowed sizes for fire compartmentation, - the measures to prevent the spread of fire to adjacent buildings, - the requirements of the materials used, depending on their location in the building - and the active measures and fire safety systems that detect fire in time, suppress it and provide enough time for safe evacuation. <p>The measures are based on the following basic parameters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - possible building users, type and population - interaction of various building spaces <p>the design and structure philosophy of buildings in Greece</p>

Scope of: (All cases that is applied)	The regulation applies to all new buildings and as it replaces older regulations, it determines which regulation for various cases of existing buildings should be followed, depending if there are any additions or changes in use of the existing buildings. For existing buildings that are not undergoing any major changes the regulation is not binding but it is recommended to be followed where possible according to “Recommended fire safety measures in existing buildings” published in May 2019 as supplementary to the regulation.																																																	
Basic requirements for buildings	<p><u>Escape routes:</u> The escape routes of a building strongly depend on the architectural design and in existing building is very difficult to change it. The requirements for the maximum lengths of an “unprotected escape route” for people gathering or educational use buildings is 18 m for single route and 35 - 45 for more routes. Emergency lighting installation with fixtures showing the building exit is mandatory and can be easily applied to existing buildings.</p> <p><u>Structural Fire safety:</u> Structural elements (Load bearing and non-load bearing, doors etc.), protected escape routes, staircases and fire compartments of a building should fulfil the fire resistance rating in minutes and category (load bearing capacity, integrity and heat insulation). Eurocodes 1-9 can be applied here for the estimation of the structural elements’ resistance to fire.</p> <p>The total floor area of independent fire compartment of a building shouldn’t exceed specific values depending on the use and height of building.</p> <p>For people gathering and education use, the minimum requirements of fire resistance are presented below:</p> <p>TABLE 5.1: FIRE RESISTANCE VALUES (GREEK REGULATION)</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="430 1014 1347 1281"> <thead> <tr> <th rowspan="3"></th> <th colspan="6">Minimum fire resistance in minutes</th> </tr> <tr> <th colspan="2">Underground floors</th> <th colspan="4">Above the ground floors</th> </tr> <tr> <th>Height>10m</th> <th>Height<10m</th> <th>Up to 2 floors</th> <th>3 to 6 floors</th> <th>7 to 10 floors and < 27m</th> <th>>27</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>People gathering</td> <td>120</td> <td>90</td> <td>60</td> <td>90</td> <td>120</td> <td>180</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Educational</td> <td>90</td> <td>60</td> <td>30</td> <td>60</td> <td>90</td> <td>120</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Depending on the category of the structural elements the fire resistance refers to one, two or all of the categories: R – load bearing capacity, E – integrity and I – heat insulation</p> <p>TABLE 5.2: CATEGORY REQUIREMENTS OF STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS (GREEK REGULATION)</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="430 1476 1352 1841"> <thead> <tr> <th>Structural Elements</th> <th>Minimum requirements</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Load bearing wall (internal/external)</td> <td>REI</td> </tr> <tr> <td>External non-load bearing, walls of fire protected escape routes and fire compartments</td> <td>EI</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Load bearing vertical elements</td> <td>R</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Fire resistant Doors, windows</td> <td>EI</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Structure elements between floors (slabs and beams)</td> <td>REI</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Staircases walls</td> <td>EI</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Load bearing elements of staircases</td> <td>R</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Minimum fire resistance in minutes						Underground floors		Above the ground floors				Height>10m	Height<10m	Up to 2 floors	3 to 6 floors	7 to 10 floors and < 27m	>27	People gathering	120	90	60	90	120	180	Educational	90	60	30	60	90	120	Structural Elements	Minimum requirements	Load bearing wall (internal/external)	REI	External non-load bearing, walls of fire protected escape routes and fire compartments	EI	Load bearing vertical elements	R	Fire resistant Doors, windows	EI	Structure elements between floors (slabs and beams)	REI	Staircases walls	EI	Load bearing elements of staircases	R
	Minimum fire resistance in minutes																																																	
	Underground floors		Above the ground floors																																															
	Height>10m	Height<10m	Up to 2 floors	3 to 6 floors	7 to 10 floors and < 27m	>27																																												
People gathering	120	90	60	90	120	180																																												
Educational	90	60	30	60	90	120																																												
Structural Elements	Minimum requirements																																																	
Load bearing wall (internal/external)	REI																																																	
External non-load bearing, walls of fire protected escape routes and fire compartments	EI																																																	
Load bearing vertical elements	R																																																	
Fire resistant Doors, windows	EI																																																	
Structure elements between floors (slabs and beams)	REI																																																	
Staircases walls	EI																																																	
Load bearing elements of staircases	R																																																	

Self-bearing roof elements (panels)	REI
-------------------------------------	-----

Spread of fire in the building: Internal staircases that are also fire protected escape routes should be of permanent structure and have a fire resistance rating of at least 60 min for 4 or less floors. Requirements are stricter for higher buildings with more population.

Piping requirements regarding the maximum allowed diameter when crossing fire compartments and when transferring flammable fluids (e.g. R32). For piping with internal diameter higher than 40mm it is not allowed to pass through fire compartments unless they are made or covered with unburnt material. The same stands for any piping carrying flammable fluids.

High risk spaces: These space are divided into two categories with the first include all typical machinery spaces, boiler rooms with power < 50 kW, storage rooms and rooms with high risk due to their nature. These spaces should be designed as separate fire compartments with at least the same fire resistance rating as the building's other fire compartments. The second category refers to spaces with higher than 50 kW boilers, transformer rooms, natural or liquid gas storage, electric vehicle charging rooms etc.

Reaction to fire requirements: For internal layers of structural products (finishings, pipe insulation, electric cables) that can be directly exposed to fire, are set by the Euroclasses and the EN 13501. The relevant requirements for people gathering and education use buildings are presented in Table 5.3.

TABLE 5.3: FIRE EUROCLASSES OF INTERNAL FINISHING (GREEK REGULATION)

	Walls and Ceilings				Floors	
	Fire protected escape routes – high risk spaces	Non fire protected escape routes	General		Fire protected escape routes– high risk spaces	Non fire protected escape routes
			Spaces > 30 m ² (40 for education)	Spaces < 30 m ² (40 for education)		
People gathering use	A2-s1,d1	C-s1,d1	D-s2,d2	C-s1,d1	B _{FL} -s2	C _{FL} -s2
Educational use	A2-s1,d1	C-s1,d1	D-s2,d2	C-s1,d1	B _{FL} -s2	C _{FL} -s2

Spread of fire outside the building: The relevant requirements refer to fire resistance rating (in min), reaction to fire rating (Euroclass) of the façade system and openings percentage requirements, depending on the distance between two adjacent buildings. Table 5.4 is valid for low rise buildings (<23m). For high rise buildings and specific type uses (like medical, social care and educational) the requirements are stricter.

TABLE 5.4: FIRE EUROCLASSES OF EXTERNAL FINISHING (GREEK REGULATION)

	Distance from adjacent building or land boundaries			
	< 3 m	3-5 m	5-10 m	>10 m

Fire resistance rating of external wall	Full requirement of table 1	Full requirement of table 1	Half requirement of table 1	No requirement
Fire reaction class of façade	B-s1,d1	B-s1,d2	C-s2,d2	D-s2,d2
Openings percentage	≤15%	≤25%	≤50%	≤80%

Active fire safety measures: The requirements are based on the type and size of buildings. For educational use the requirements are: Fire extinguishers: 1 per floor area of 150m². Manual fire alarm system is mandatory for population of over 50 persons. Automated fire detection system is also mandatory for educational buildings of more than 4 floors, for laboratory use space (physics, chemistry, PC). Permanent water supply dedicated for fire safety is for buildings above 4 floors or 4000 m². All other buildings should be equipped with a

5.3.2.4 Accessibility, safety and hygiene & protection against noise – acoustics

Country	Greece
Category	Protection against noise – acoustics / Hygiene, health and the environment
Regulation Original Title	ΚΤΗΡΟΔΟΜΙΚΟΣ ΚΑΝΟΝΙΣΜΟΣ
English translation of title	BUILDING STRUCTURES REGULATION
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	1989, Amendment 2023
Document type & Status	Type: Regulations, codes with legal status Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	The regulation is applied countrywide
Brief summary / content description	<p>The building structures regulation is a more generic regulation that covers all aspects of infrastructure use, including its construction, with a more descriptive approach and in some cases with specific requirements.</p> <p>The building structures regulation aims to regulate the construction of infrastructures in order to serve their intended use and under normal conditions of maintenance and for an acceptable lifetime to satisfy the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Comfort, health, wellbeing and safety of residents and users - Quality, safety, durability, aesthetics and functionality of buildings - Protection of the environment - Facilitate and promote scientific research in the construction field

	<p>Increase of productivity in the building construction field</p>
<p>Scope of: (All cases that is applied)</p>	<p>The regulation has a generic application to all type of buildings and infrastructure in all regions and of the country. The regulation defines all types of building use.</p>
<p>Basic requirements for buildings</p>	<p>The regulation defines the typical population of each type of building use and sets the maximum allowed number of people per area for types of building use where people are gathered or waiting. It refers to safety and durability of buildings both in the stage of construction, use and maintenance by setting precaution measures and referring to other regulations like the ones that specify the requirements for structural stability and fire safety</p> <p>The regulation defines the clear internal height and volume that the buildings should have. It defines all types of building walls, openings and windows/doors.</p> <p>All types of walls and windows should have stability in case of an earthquake, wind resistance, fire resistance, thermal insulation, sound insulation, waterproofing, resistance to solar radiation, mechanical strength under normal conditions, stability of any layers they are covered with. Most of the above are covered by other regulations apart from sound performance for which there is a specific article on this one described further below.</p> <p>The regulation sets basic requirements for walls on the boundaries of the premises that a building is built in, for fencing and stairs inside and outside of a building. It continues setting some basic requirements of accessibility (for all internal spaces and surrounding area of a building) and for green spaces that are specified more in other regulations.</p> <p>The regulation deals also with natural daylight and natural ventilation in buildings. All spaces with a primary use (not auxiliary use) should in general have access to natural daylight and natural ventilation. It is allowed for specific building types not having natural ventilation when there is sufficient mechanical ventilation and there is a full study and approve by the appropriate organization. Natural and direct daylight and natural ventilation is mandatory for main spaces of residential buildings. All residential spaces should have adequate natural ventilation and daylight. A space that is considered to have adequate daylight should have openings to the external environment with an area of at least 10% of the space floor area. Only the glazing area of the opening that is above 1.20m from the floor is taken into account. A space that is considered to have direct natural ventilation should have openings to the external environment with an area of at least 5% of the space floor area. Natural ventilation is mandatory in residential buildings, even if mechanical ventilation is applied.</p> <p>A requirement for a quantified ventilation rate is given for every building use, in the technical guidebook for energy performance of buildings calculation (<i>T.O.T.E.E 20701-1/2017</i>) based on some relevant Greek and international standards</p>

Specific requirements for **noise protection** are set in Article 22 of the regulation and for buildings constructed after the publication of the regulation. The requirements set three categories:

- A) High acoustic comfort
- B) Normal acoustic comfort
- C) Low acoustic comfort

All all new buildings should belong at least to category B. Acoustic comfort of a space is defined by a set of acoustic parameters related to the sound insulation and protection from noise of the space from:

- Airborne noise generated in adjacent spaces
- Impact noise generated in adjacent spaces
- Airborne noise generated in common private spaces of the same building
- Airborne noise generated from external sources

Parameters: R_w , R'_w , $L'_{n,w}$, $L_{Aeg,h}$, L_{pA} are defined in the following table and the maximum values for a space to belong to category A, B or C are presented in the next tables:

TABLE 5.5: ACOUSTIC COMFORT PARAMETERS (GREEK REGULATION)

Type of noise	Parameter of acoustic comfort			Measured quantity		
	Name	Symbol	Unit	Name	Symbol	Unit
Protection from airborne noise	<i>Weighted Sound Reduction Index</i>	R_w	dB	<i>Sound Reduction Index</i>	R	dB
	<i>Weighted apparent Sound Reduction Index</i>	R'_w	dB	<i>Apparent Sound Reduction Index</i>	R'	dB
Protection from impact noise	weighted, <i>standardised impact sound pressure level</i>	$L'_{n,w}$	dB	<i>standardised impact sound pressure level</i>	L'_n	dB
Protection from airborne noise – external sources	Soundlevel - A	$L_{Aeg,h}$	dB (A)	Soundlevel - A	L_{pA}	dB (A)
Protection from airborne noise – from facilities	Soundlevel - A	L_{pA}	dB (A)	Soundlevel - A	L_{pA}	dB (A)

For category A – High Acoustic comfort for buildings with people gathering uses:

TABLE 5.6: THRESHOLDS FOR HIGH ACOUSTIC COMFORT (GREEK REGULATION)

		External noises	Noises of building facilities				
R'_w	$L'_{n,w}$	$L_{Aeq,h}$	L_{pA}	R'_w	R'_w	$L'_{n,w}$	
65	40	25	25	-	65	40	

For category B – Normal Acoustic comfort for for buildings with people gathering uses:

TABLE 5.7: THRESHOLDS FOR NORMAL ACOUSTIC COMFORT (GREEK REGULATION)

Noise protection from adjacent space (of primary, secondary or common use)		Noise protection from		Noise reduction from spaces of the same residence	Noise reduction of a primary space from building facilities spaces	
		External noises	Noises of building facilities			
R'_w	$L'_{n,w}$	$L_{Aeq,h}$	L_{pA}	R'_w	R'_w	$L'_{n,w}$
60	45	25	25	-	62	45

This regulation was never really applied in practice. In 2010 a new regulation was suggested by the Greek Institute of Acoustics that was updating and reforming the previous one. Unfortunately, this new suggested regulation is still not officially active and in practice it is not mandatory to perform an acoustics study when constructing a new residential building.

Finally, the regulation sets the basic requirements about all technical systems and services of a building:

- Plumbing
- Waste, sewage and rainwater
- Water supply
- Water active fire safety
- Heating
- Cooling & ventilation
- Elevators
- Electrical installation and networks
- Thunder safety

Special regulations of all categories mentioned in the regulations precede this regulation

5.3.2.5 Energy performance

Country	Greece
Category	Energy performance of buildings (EPBD/EED transposition)

Regulation Original Title	ΚΑΝΟΝΙΣΜΟΣ ΕΝΕΡΓΕΙΑΚΗΣ ΑΠΟΔΟΣΗΣ ΚΤΗΡΙΩΝ (ΚΕΝΑΚ)
English translation of title	REGULATION on the ENERGY PERFORMANCE OF BUILDINGS
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2010, 2017 revision
Document type & Status	Type: Regulations, codes with legal status Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	The regulation is applied countrywide
Brief summary / content description	<p>The Greek Regulation on the Energy Performance of Buildings aims at reducing energy consumption for heating, cooling, DHW and lighting of buildings ensuring at the same time comfort and quality of the indoor build environment. It defines the methodology for calculating the energy performance of buildings by estimating energy consumption for heating, cooling, DHW and lighting. It sets the minimum requirements and the classification of building energy performance. It also prescribes the type and the content of Energy Performance Study of buildings as well as the procedure of energy inspection of buildings and its systems after which an Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) is issued.</p> <p>The above is facilitated with a series of technical guidebooks published by the technical chamber of Greece and approved by the respective ministry.</p>
Scope of: (All cases that is applied)	<p>The regulation applies to all buildings consuming energy for regulating the indoor conditions for ensuring the comforts of their users. The Energy Performance Study is obligatory for all new and all deeply renovated buildings. Issuing an EPC is mandatory, apart from new and deeply renovated buildings, when a building is sold or leased and for all public buildings larger than 250 m² of total floor area.</p> <p>In addition, when a building element or system is installed or replaced post initial construction has to satisfy the minimum requirements of the regulation to the extent that its technically, functionally and economically feasible.</p>
Definition of ZeB / nZeB-standard	<p>ZeB is not yet defined. Currently in Greece, nZEB are considered all the buildings that are class A for new buildings and class B+ for existing, in the Energy Performance Certificate scale without any more specific requirements or quantitative limitations in consumption or generation from RES. The Greek nZEB definition was given in the National Plan for Increasing nZEB and according to the latest voted Greek law (4819/2021 on 23/07/2021) all new buildings from the beginning of 2021, should be nZEB (class A) (an extension period was given till May that B+ were also allowed).</p>
	Basic requirements set by the Regulation:

1. Building Envelope: Individual building elements of the building envelope have to fulfil the following requirements concerning their insulating properties, which are differentiated if it's a new or existing building and they also depend on the climate zone the building belongs (4 climate zones within Greece also defined by the regulation itself).
The maximum allowed heat transfer coefficient of every element of **new buildings** and in every climate zone, is presented in the table below:

TABLE 5.8: MAXIMUM U-VALUES FOR NEW BUILDINGS (GREEK REGULATION)

Building element	Max U – Value [W/m ² K]			
	Climate Zone			
	A	B	C	D
External horizontal or inclined roof	0.45	0.40	0.35	0.30
External wall	0.55	0.45	0.40	0.35
Wall adjacent to unheated space or ground	1.30	0.90	0.70	0.65
External floor	0.45	0.40	0.35	0.30
Floor adjacent to unheated space or ground	1.10	0.80	0.65	0.60
External openings (windows/doors)	2.80	2.60	2.40	2.20
Openings adjacent to unheated space or ground	5.00	4.60	4.30	4.00

There is also a maximum allowed average U value for the whole building including thermal bridges which depends on the Total External Area to total volume ratio (A/V)

TABLE 5.9: MAXIMUM U_m VALUES FOR NEW BUILDINGS (GREEK REGULATION)

A/V Ratio	Max U _m – Value [W/m ² K]			
	Climate Zone			
	A	B	C	D
≤ 0.2	1.25	1.13	1.04	0.95
0.3	1.17	1.05	0.96	0.88
0.4	1.10	0.99	0.91	0.83
0.5	1.04	0.93	0.86	0.78
0.6	0.98	0.89	0.81	0.73
0.7	0.92	0.83	0.76	0.68
0.8	0.86	0.77	0.71	0.63
0.9	0.80	0.73	0.65	0.59
≥ 1.0	0.77	0.69	0.62	0.55

2. Building (technical) systems:

- a) All piping networks (water or other fluid) should be insulated according to the Technical Guidebooks accompanying the regulation. For space heating/cooling the minimum requirements

	<p>of the insulation of the piping is 19mm and 13mm for DHW with a thermal conductivity of $\lambda=0.040$ W/mK. Piping networks should also have a regulation system for a reduced energy consumption under partial load.</p> <p>b) For new buildings and where feasible for existing, there is a minimum solar fraction for DHW of 60% requirement unless there is another type of RES system, district heating or high efficiency heat pumps.</p> <p>c) When there is a central heating, cooling or DHW system there should be calorific measurement for cost allocation and at least a thermostat per autonomous space.</p> <p>All technical systems of the building or building unit should comply with the 2012/27/EU directive that was amended with the 2018/2002 directive.</p>
--	---

5.3.2.6 Sustainable use of natural resources – Nature based/bio/recycled/reused materials

Country	Greece
Category	Construction waste management
Regulation Original Title	Μέτρα, όροι και πρόγραμμα για την εναλλακτική διαχείριση των αποβλήτων από εκσκαφές, κατασκευές και κατεδαφίσεις (ΚΥΑ 36259/1757/Ε103/2010)
English translation of title	Terms, measures and program for alternative management of waste materials from excavations, constructions and deconstructions (Joint Ministerial Decision 36259/1757/E103/2010)
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2010
Document type & Status	Type: Joint Ministerial Decree Status: Approved and in force
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	The regulation is applied countrywide
Brief summary / content description	The program targets to minimize all waste from excavation, construction and deconstruction works by reducing the quantity of disposable waste, reusing and recycling them.
Scope of: (All cases that is applied)	The decision applies to all waste from the mentioned activities and refers to any type, volume or weight of waste materials. It also includes marble waste from marble cutting as well as concrete surplus. Exemptions are made for hazardous waste materials, for waste from mineral extractions and for soil and natural materials that are going to be reused in the same site in the same form.

Basic terms & requirements	The Decree sets the basic obligations that the waste managers of a project have in order to ensure that the waste materials will be forwarded to appropriate recycling sites. Terms for the collection and transport of waste are described, as well as for the facilities of waste process. It also sets national goals for the fraction of the reusable and recycled waste weight which was targeted to reach 70% in 2020. Finally, dissemination, audits and penalties are described concerning the application of the terms.
----------------------------	--

5.3.2.7 RES regulatory framework

Country	Greece
Category	Renewable energy sources in buildings – PV systems & net metering in buildings
Regulation Original Title	-
English translation of title	Not a regulation – Legal framework regarding PV systems in buildings and net metering (based on the law 4513 of 2018 ministerial decree of Ministry of Energy 15084/382 in 2019)
Publication year / amendment year (if any)	2018, 2019, (in 2023 it was announced that the framework will be modified and the term “net-metering” will change to “net-billing”)
Document type & Status	The laws are applied countrywide
Region of enforcement (If differentiated countrywide)	Type: Laws, ministerial decrees Status: Approved and in force
Brief summary / content description	The legal framework describes the terms and procedures for power generation with the method of net metering and virtual net metering at buildings or energy communities with all kinds of renewable energy sources (photovoltaics, small wind turbines, biogas, biomass, CHP, small hydroelectric stations)
Scope of: (All cases that is applied)	The framework applies for all kind of building owners/users and consumers both physical and legal entities as well as private and public
Basic terms	<p>Net-metering with no energy storage</p> <p>In general, when the net-metering connection is applied, a PV system installed in a building is connected with the grid and for a given period the user pays to the energy provider the difference between the energy consumed and generated onsite or else the net electricity consumption. The energy does not have to be necessarily consumed at the same time as generated. The terms for a net-metering connection are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The maximum kWp of the PV system depends on the type and size of the electrical supply from the energy provider and the type of the applicant. <p>TABLE 5.10: MAXIMUM ALLOWED PV SYSTEM POWER (GREEK REGULATION)</p>

Voltage level	No of grid supply	Agreed Power of supply (kVA)	Maximum allowed PV system power (kWp) for interconnected mainland	
			Physical or legal entities	Public entities. Energy communities
Low Single phase	03	8	5	5
	05	12	5	5
Low – 3 phase	1	15	15	15
	2	25	20	25
	3	35	20	35
	4	55	27.5	55
	5	85	42.5	85
	6	135	67.5	100
Medium	-	-	100% of Agreed Power up to 1MWp	100% of Agreed Power up to 1MWp
			100	100

It also depends if the consumer is on the continental Greece or the non-interconnected islands.

- The PV system should be installed in the same space/building with the consumption facilities or to an adjacent space
- Natural and legal entities are eligible for a net-metering connection as long as they are owners of the building they want to install the PV system or they have legal right of use of the building after the owner’s written consent.
- It is possible to install a PV system in a common space of a building (e.g. roof) after the consent of all the related owners.
- Every PV system can be related with only one individual power supply (meter).
- The net-metering PV system can only be installed in a permanent power supply and be registered at the same name of the person also registered in the power supply.
- The calculation of the net consumption is made in 3 years’ basis and there is no compensation if the generated electricity is more than the consumed one.
- It can be applied for both single and three-phase systems (max 5 kWp for single phase) and only three phase PV system can be installed in a three phase power supply.
- Both generated and consumed electricity should be measured at a net-metering system. The typical electricity supply meter should measure both directions of power flow between the grid and the consumer and a second meter should measure only the generation of the PV system.
- The net-metering pricing depends always on the timing of the electricity generation and consumption. This means that the higher the concurrency of PV generation and building consumption, the higher the benefit.

Net-metering with energy storage

	<p>Since 2019, it is possible for a PV system to be installed with a net-metering connection and with a permanent energy storage system (array of batteries). With the addition of storage in a building the level of generation and consumption concurrency rises and as so does the benefit.</p> <p>The following additional terms stand when there is energy storage:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The storage system is considered as part of the internal electrical installation of the building and should comply with all relevant national and international standards and regulations. • The storage system is connected in parallel with the grid. • The operation of the storage system ensures that there is no exchange of energy between itself and the grid which means that the energy stored in it, comes exclusively from the PV system as well as the stored energy is provided exclusively to the consumptions of the building. • The nominal power (in kVA) of the storage system inverter should not exceed the total installed kWp of the PV system with a maximum of 30 kVA. In addition, the power of the inverter should be such in order for the maximum current that may occur from both the PV system and the storage system not to exceed the maximum load of the electrical supply. <p>Net-Billing</p> <p>Net-billing method is about to take place the net-metering however the specific terms are not yet published. The major difference is that the energy that is generated on-site and is not consumed will be sold to the grid. However, feed in tariff is not expected to be very attractive in order to promote installations with storage.</p> <p>Autonomous PV system</p> <p>Even if there is no legal framework for a building with an autonomous PV system, it is possible for a building to have one as long as there is no connection to the grid.</p>
--	---

5.3.3 Compliance challenges

In Greece, traditional houses constructed at least around 100 years ago, are made mostly of stone and wood. However, modern constructions rarely use natural materials for their load bearing structures and apart from wooden roofs, such materials are limited for finishing and decorations purposes. Seismic regulation may reduce the contribution of natural materials to the total construction and increase the use of conventional ones.

Natural insulation materials like sheep wool is examined however the non-standardised properties may stand as a barrier for its application. Reaction to fire as well as vapor and humidity resistance are some of the properties that might not be appropriate enough for using it as a building insulation material. Special treatment and process of the natural insulation materials could be a solution to the challenge.

Another issue that might be challenging is the renewable energy sources systems that will be installed on the building. According to the GreenNest project early design and the GA, building integrated PV (BIPV) systems will be the major renewable energy system. Use of BIPVs that does not alters the aesthetics of the roof tiles is in any case mandatory due to the traditional character of the region. However, blending with the natural roof construction comes with a reduction in efficiency. Thus, the possible challenge is if the total PV installed power will be sufficient to generate the amount of energy needed to reach ZeB level.

5.4 Other national standards and conclusions

5.4.1 Standards on earth construction from various countries

The last few decades there is a revival of interest in earth construction. The main reasons in brief are the healthier indoor environment, the abatement of emissions, the recyclability and reusability potential of earthen materials, the regulation of humidity and the high thermal inertia if compared with conventional building materials as concrete. This increased attention is reflected in both the research field, with a tenfold increase of the published studies in a single decade [25], as well as in the development of the legislator framework.

According to surveys conducted by Reddy et al. [26], Schroeder [27] [28] [29], Delgado and Guerero [30] and Cid et al. that were reviewed [31], there are about 20 countries that have regulated earth construction and there are more than 80 standards on earthen structures and materials. Nonetheless, all of them are regional or national and there are hardly any global standards published by the International Standards Organization (ISO). It should be mentioned that according to ISO, a clear distinction should be made between standards and normative documents. A standard is published by a national organization of standardization and has to be accepted by a national authority body. A normative document is not issued by a national organization of standardization, but by specialized organizations that have passed a predefined procedure of approval. Usually, they are not recognized by a state building authority however, they could attain the quality of a standard and be confirmed by a national authority body [28] [29].

TABLE 5.11: COUNTRIES WITH STANDARDS/NORMATIVE DOCUMENTS ON EARTH CONSTRUCTION

Type	Countries
National Standard	New Zealand, USA (ASTM and Regional Standards in the states of New Mexico and California), Kenya, Nigeria, Tunisia, Zimbabwe, Cameroon, Burkina Faso, India, Kyrgystan, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Brazil, Peru, Chile, Mexico, Colombia, France, Germany, Spain, Turkey
Normative Document	Switzerland, Australia, Spain, Germany, Portugal

In Table 5.11, the countries that have established standards or normative documents for earth building are presented. In Europe, which is the focus of this report, France, Germany and Spain have issued standards, while Switzerland and Portugal have normative documents. More specifically:

- In **Switzerland**, Regeln zum Bauen mit Lehm [32], published in 1994, is a normative document covering various earth building techniques, including light clay. It's the only standard that specifies a minimum strength for light clay, which is set at 0.5 MPa. The regulations were developed by a team from the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology (ETH) after two years of research commissioned by the Swiss Federal Office of Energy.

- In **France** there is AFNOR XP.P13-901 [33] published in 2001 by the French Standard Association with the status of a National Standard. It refers to Earth Blocks providing both Granularity and plasticity nomograms to assess and modify the suitability of the soil.
- In **Spain** there are:
 - A) UNE 41410 [34], “Compressed earth blocks for structural and partition walls. Definitions, specifications and test procedures” issued in 2008 with the status of a standard. It covers various aspects of both stabilised and unstabilised compressed earth blocks, as soil selection, appropriate moulds and machinery, testing procedures and quality control.
 - B) MOPT Tapial [35] “Bases para el diseño y construcción con tapial” published in 1992 by the Ministry of Public Works and Transport is a Normative Document about Rammed Earth. An interesting point of this document is that, besides testing procedures, it provides design values of unconfined compressed strength.
- In **Germany** there are three standards and one normative document:
 - A) DIN 18945 [36] is a national standard published in 2013 and revised in 2018 referring to earth blocks without differentiation between compressed or non-compressed blocks. It’s the strictest as far as strength is concerned (table 1) with a minimum average strength of 2.50 N/mm². Its also very precise regarding the procedures to assess the compressive strength and all the mechanical parameters, which are a matter of dispute and methods from either concrete or calcined bricks have been found ineffective [37] [38]. Moisture behavior (assessed with dip test), thermal conductivity (assessed with the guarded hot plate method), specific heat capacity and fire performance are also regulated.
 - B) DIN 18946 [39] is also a national standard issued in 2013 and revised in 2018 and again in 2023. It is a standard on earth mortars that is heavily relying on EN 1015 [40], since the specimens size, the moulds (40x40x160mm) and the methods to determine consistency/workability (EN 1015-3 [41]) as well as compressive and flexural strength (EN 1015-11 [42]), are based on the abovementioned European Standard. Strength classes are also provided and a minimum strength of 2 N/mm² is suggested for mortars for load-bearing masonry. Thermal properties, Resistance to water, Volume change and fire performance are also regulated. A system for monitoring the constancy of performance is also suggested.
 - C) DIN 18947 [43] is a national standard introduced in 2013 and revised in 2018 and 2024. It’s a standard on earth plasters referring to the whole plastering system and the different layers: The base coat, the top coat and the finish. Besides compressive strength classes, minimum values for other important parameters for a plaster, as the adhesive strength, the flexural strength and the resistance to abrasion are defined. As in the case of the other DIN standards, thermal properties, resistance to water, fire performance and a system for monitoring the constancy of performance is suggested.
 - D) Lehmbau Regeln [44] incorporates new developments in earth construction and has the status of a normative document. As shown schematically in figure 1, Lehmbau Regeln consists of three parts: One for the construction soil, one for the earthen building materials and one for the earth building

elements. Among the standards and normative documents, Lehmbau Regeln is the one that covers the most earth building materials and earth building methods. It's also one of the few that provides information not only at the material level, but also at the masonry and building level, such as minimum wall thickness and maximum slenderness

- In **Portugal** the National Laboratory (LNEC) published in 1953 a normative document entitled “Earth use as building material” (in Portuguese) [45]. It includes guidelines about the earth composition and focuses on the technique of rammed earth.
- In **Italy** there is L.R. 2/06 [46] published in 2006. It's a regional standard for the restoration/conservation of earthen building structures. Another Italian regional regulation about earthen structures in Italy is Ley n° 378: 2004 [47]

6 Deriving specifications for EU target markets

The current document is mostly a review-oriented deliverable attempting to match EU and national regulatory framework with the three demo cases in three different countries. All demo cases are about new constructions, new buildings that are going to adopt characteristics of zero-emission and sustainable elements in terms of low embodied carbon emissions utilising circular economy. Based on the latest updates of the EU directives regarding buildings and sustainability, EU sets the beginning of the zero-emission buildings. Apart from zero on-site fossil fuel emissions and the operation stage, the content of embodied carbon emissions in the building elements will have to be measured and given in the building energy performance certificate.

6.1 ZeB definition

As it was described in section 4.6, EU defines ZeB setting explicitly the zero on-site carbon emissions requirement. Apart from this, it leaves the member states to come up with the detailed threshold of energy demand and operational greenhouse emissions. Since national definitions of ZeB are not yet available, GreeNest project should define its “own” definition that will attempted to be applied in the demonstration buildings. To do so, the boundaries within which zero emissions are taken into account should be set. Figure

FIGURE 6.1 MODULAR SCHEMATIC OF BUILDING LIFE CYCLE STAGES ACCORDING TO EN:15978-2011

6.1 shows the basic life cycle stages of a building according to EN 15978:2011 (Sustainability of construction works - Assessment of environmental performance of buildings - Calculation method).

Based on these stages and if they are taken into account, the Research Centre about zero emission buildings of Norway separates six different ZeB levels [53], as shown in Figure 6.2.

FIGURE 6.2: ZEB CATEGORIES OF ZERO EMISSION BUILDINGS FOR NORWAY

These levels are explained right below:

ZEB – O: The building's renewable energy production compensates for greenhouse gas emissions from **operation** of the building.

ZEB – O ÷ EQ: The building's renewable energy production compensates for greenhouse gas emissions from **operation of the building minus the energy use for equipment** (plug loads).

ZEB – OM: The building's renewable energy production compensates for greenhouse gas emissions from **operation and production of its building materials**.

ZEB – COM: The building's renewable energy production compensates for greenhouse gas emissions from **construction, operation and production of building materials**

ZEB – COMPLETE: The building's renewable energy production compensates for greenhouse gas emissions from the **entire lifespan** of the building. Building materials – construction – operation and demolition/recycling.

The first two levels include only operational energy use and emissions. Second level excludes the equipment energy use which according the JRC [17] is called non-building related energy use.

Next three levels include embodied emissions gradually including processes from the production of the construction materials, the construction of the building itself and finally the end of life demolition/disposal/recycle of the materials. The production of the materials includes their transport to the site.

Another product with GWP used in buildings is the refrigerant of the heating and cooling systems, driving usually chillers and heat pumps, even though it is not included in the previous definitions. Apart from the EU F-gas regulation, described in section 4.7, the recently published US ZeB definition clearly includes minimizing the impact of refrigerants as a requirement for reducing a buildings life cycle emissions [48].

6.2 Deriving ZeB Specifications

6.2.1 Basic requirements

Demonstrator buildings of GreeNest project should fulfil the basic requirements of the EPBD definition that all EU members will eventually have to transpose in their national building energy performance regulatory framework. The ZeB requirements and the respective specifications that should be followed at the demonstration cases of the project are:

TABLE 6.1: BASIC REQUIREMENTS FOR ZEB

	Requirement	Specification	Challenges
1	Zero onsite carbon emissions produced	No fossil fuel will be consumed on site of the GreeNest DC buildings (meaning inside the building boundaries) e.g. gas boilers	No particular challenge detected.
2	Energy demand will be at least 10 % less than the respective NZEB requirement	Energy demand of GreeNest DC buildings will be 10% less than the respective NZEB based on the necessary calculations with the appropriate software specified by the respective national regulation.	NZEB definition varies for each EU country and there is not always an energy demand/consumption specific benchmark. For example, in Greece, according to KENAK, NZEB is a building with at last energy class A.
3	Operational energy consumption will be covered by onsite renewable energy generation so as operational emissions will be compensated.	GreeNest DC buildings on site energy generation from renewable sources should at least cover the consumption.	Covering the buildings' operational consumption could be challenging due to limitation to available area with direct sunlight and strongly related to the national regulatory

			<p>framework. In addition, depending on the type and period of use, on-site generation and consumption might not happen at the same time creating imbalance and making energy storage systems rather mandatory.</p>
--	--	--	---

6.2.2 Reduction of Embodied emissions

From that point and beyond, further reducing emissions by choosing eco friendlier, recycled materials, based on a local value chain will be an additional goal. As a result, the embodied emissions of all the other building life stages should be reduced in comparison with conventional constructions:

- a) Construction materials – embodied carbon for extraction, production and transportation of the raw materials, processed materials, building elements and technical systems.
- b) Construction process
- c) End of life – deconstruction, disposal, recycling/potential reuse

Ensuring reduced embodied emissions means that for all the three phases described, LCA will be carried out and GWP will be estimated for each and every component and process. According to the GA the reduction of the embodied emissions will be 50% less than a building constructed at NZEB standard. This actually means a typical construction fulfilling the current energy performance requirements, as there is no requirement for the embodied emissions.

GreeNest project is based on the fulfilment of the above request deploying various mapping tools and procedures regarding all materials, components, SPs and even processes that will be utilized for the installation of the SPs in the DC buildings.

6.3 Target market definition

EU states clearly through the new EPBD that that all new public buildings should be ZeB by 2028 and by 2030 the same stands for private buildings. The EU regulatory framework shows the importance of the sustainability of products in general and construction products, process and buildings in particular. All regulations are lining up in the same direction of sustainability reduction of operational and embodied emissions and circular economy.

EU Regulatory framework

FIGURE 6.3: EU INTERRELATED REGULATORY FRAMEWORK [39].

All EU countries sooner or later will have to adopt the directive with some room for national adjustments of the requirements. GreenNest is targeting directly the construction markets of the three countries where the DC buildings are going to be constructed. Typologies of the four DC buildings themselves are different in use, shape and size. However, all of DC buildings types could be of public ownership and use which is significant due to the requirements of ZeB by 2028 & 2030 about zero operational emissions and fully recorded embodied ones.

As a result, each one of the demo buildings will be a pioneer in the country that is constructed as ZeB (even though national specific definitions are yet to be specified) and accompanied with the GWP of all of its stages. Apart from ZeB, GreenNest targets the construction markets that will in any case include the local and/or regional value chains for the construction materials.

6.3.1 German target market

DC#1: Pavilion Museum is a future-oriented concept made of reclaimed wood with a foundation made of recycled materials and a low-tech approach. The proposed design emphasizes ecological ZeB construction,

with eco-friendly design solutions that will be visible for visitors and part of future exhibitions, conferences, seminars, knowledge days for professionals, students and visitors.

The selection of DC#1 is quite suitable for the German market that has a full regulatory framework for timber constructions and an adequate level of maturity for recycled timber apart from the certification and the product development of waste-wood which is pursued to be realized in the frame of GreenNest.

Consequently, the target market that is directly aimed by the project could be:

The construction of ZeB, private or public building, small to medium size, with relevant mixed use and based mostly on timber construction.

DC#2: The design of the Berlin – Lodge, the second demonstration building in Germany, is quite preliminary and will not be fully studied and constructed under the GreenNest specification as it will mainly incorporate a specific SP (EcoTechWall, SP11). However, it will provide an insight from the construction market for residential buildings.

6.3.2 Italian target market

DC#3: The Delta demo building will operate as tourist info point but also, as a warehouse for fishermen. This special use of the building visited and used by many different people all year long makes it an exemplary building to demonstrate ZeB and use of materials and construction products with low embodied emissions.

The market targeted in this case is that of small size public buildings located in areas of natural beauty and environmental significance. The added value of more sustainable construction and materials fully aligned with the upcoming era of ZeB are promoted while the active involvement of local resources suppliers makes it even more attractive for municipalities and regional authorities.

6.3.3 Greek target market

DC#4: The North Aegean demo building will serve as museum and recreation center located in a traditional village of Lesvos island. The new building will be a part of an old building complex that used to produce olive oil. The building will be constructed in a very unique location in a village where buildings are typically constructed with natural materials like stone and wood and also located in a relatively remote island.

At first glance, the target market may appear limited; however, Greece is full of regions with similar characteristics, rural villages with traditional constructions that used to exploit or in several cases are still exploiting local resources for building materials as well as local expertise that preserves various traditional techniques. What is more, after the economic recession of 2010 it was observed a significant return to small towns and villages from big city centers. Introduction of ZeB buildings with emphasis to reduction in embodied emissions of construction materials and process in such a place could be easily replicated in similar regions.

As the requirement set by the EU will start a couple of years for public buildings, in order to set the scenery of ZeB, market targeted in the beginning is mostly the ones of municipalities and regional authorities and new small to medium size constructions with an open and public function. However, as traditional regions in Greece often attract tourists mainly from Europe, a transition for example to the market of traditional guest houses and small hotels seems like a possibility.

6.4 Standardization and certification

As it is described in the GA, GreenNest will utilize 16 Standardized Packages (SPs) with some of them being innovative materials or building components and other being tools or schemes. Especially for the material and component ones, they will need to be certified in order to successfully enter the construction market. Due to their innovative character the absence of a dedicated certification framework is highly likely. For this reason, a certification pathway should be set containing the respective requirements set by EU or national regulations. In this section, a preliminary reference of the certification strategy is given, before the subsequent work on certification requirements, where the certification and standardization roadmap will be created in order for the SPs to be integrated into the EU and national codes.

The three SP that are characterized as materials can follow the route of a simple construction product and by receiving any required safety and product performance certification needed for further deployment of the material including: determination of fire safety class; environmental product declaration acc. EN 15804 and verification of thermal insulation and mechanical properties e.g. thermal resistance of insulating products according to EN 13162.

The SPs that represent more complex products (e.g. envelope systems) will consist of multiple components that many of them could be already standardised commercial products. This fact facilitates the development of innovative solutions (use of well-known products as much as possible) so that effort can be put in the innovative goals such as integration of the different components, manufacturing processes for the industrialisation of systems, combination of new functionalities, etc.

The commercial products will therefore need to comply with the applicable European legislation when put on the market, regardless of their use as integrated products in a constructive system (SP).

7 Conclusion

The current document is the first deliverable report of the GreeNest project and is dedicated to the the current and continuously evolving EU and national regulatory landscape often attract tourists. Apart from the standard regulatory framework of constructions and buildings, emphasis has been given to the recently reviewed EU directives for building energy performance and for sustainable products (EPBD & ESPR). These areas are strongly connected with GreeNest objectives and ambitions.

Regulations have to be strictly followed in the progress of the project and more specific to both the design of the demonstrator buildings and the GreeNest ecosystem with all the SPs that will be utilized. Apart from this, early regulation compliance challenges were identified based on the preliminary designs, for the best preparation of the project. Next, the major specifications of the demonstration case buildings were derived, in terms of ZeB definition and further reduction of embodied emissions of the various building stages. These specifications are in any case the cornerstones of the project and have to be early addressed.

Finally, functioning as an introductory deliverable, the report provides a short target market definition and a preliminary certification roadmap which in later stages will be developed for the GreeNest ecosystem.

8 References

- [1] "European Commission JOINT RESEARCH CENTER - About the EN Eurocodes," [Online]. Available: <https://eurocodes.jrc.ec.europa.eu/showpage.php?id=1>.
- [2] VVA Economics & Policy, Joint Institute for Innovation Policy (JIIP), Danish, "Supporting study for the Review of the Construction Products Regulation: Evaluation - Final Report," European Commission, 2018.
- [3] Council of the European Union, REGULATION (EU) No 305/2011 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL, European Union, 2011.
- [4] F. Pacheco-Torgal, "Introduction to the environmental impact of construction and building materials," Eco-efficient Construction and Building Materials, pp. 1-10, ISBN, 978-0-85709-767-5, 2014.
- [5] J. Cremers, "Environmental impact of architectural fabric structures," Fabric Structures in Architecture, 2015.
- [6] "European Commission - Declaration of Performance (DoP) and CE marking," [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/growth/sectors/construction/product-regulation/performance-declaration_en.
- [7] SUMMARY OF: Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 — harmonised conditions for the marketing of construction products.
- [8] European Commission, "European Commission - Joint Research Centre - Eurocodes," [Online]. Available: <https://eurocodes.jrc.ec.europa.eu/showpage.php?id=1>.
- [9] "Danish Standards - Eurocodes - Frequently Asked Questions," [Online]. Available: <https://www.ds.dk/en/our-services/eurocodes/eurocodes-frequently-asked-questions>.
- [10] BAM , BRE , Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs (European Commission) , Efectis , EMI , RISE Safety, "Development of a European approach to assess the fire performance of facades," EU Publications, 2018.
- [11] "www.ri.se," [Online]. Available: <https://www.ri.se/en/what-we-do/projects/finalisation-of-the-european-approach-to-assess-the-fire-performance-of-facades>.
- [12] PU Europe FIRE SAFETY HANDBOOK, 2020.

- [13] J. Elizondo-Urrestarazu, "Strategy for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2021-2030: A view from Equality Bodies," EQUINET - European Network of Equality Bodies, 2021.
- [14] E. Parliament, "DIRECTIVE 2002/49/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 25 June 2002 relating to the assessment and management of environmental noise.," Official Journal of the EU, 2002.
- [15] B. Rasmussen, "Acoustic classification of buildings in Europe – Main characteristics of national schemes for housing, schools, hospitals and office buildings," Danish Building Research Institute (SBI), Aalborg University Copenhagen, Denmark, 2018.
- [16] B. Rasmussen, "Building acoustic regulations in Europe Brief history and actual situation," in Baltic-Nordic Acoustics Meeting 2018At: Harpa, Reykjavik, Iceland, 2019.
- [17] C. M. G. D. B. P. Joint Research Centre - JRC (Maduta, "Defining Zero-Emission Buildings - Support for the revision of the EPBD," Joint Research Centre - JRC.
- [18] DIRECTIVE (EU) 2024/1275 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on the energy performance of buildings, Official Journal of the European Union, April 2024.
- [19] European Commission, "Energy efficiency directive," 2023. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/energy/topics/energy-efficiency/targets-directive-and-rules/energy-efficiency-directive_en#content-heading-0.
- [20] "ECO-platform," 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.eco-platform.org/eco-epd-40.html>.
- [21] "Revised Construction Products Regulation (CPR) to include EPD data | One Click LCA," OneClickLCA, [Online]. Available: <https://oneclicklca.com/en/resources/articles/revised-construction-products-regulation-to-include-epd-data>.
- [22] "OneClickLCA," [Online]. Available: <https://www.oneclicklca.com/simple-epd-guide/>.
- [23] "European Commission - About sustainable products," [Online]. Available: https://commission.europa.eu/energy-climate-change-environment/standards-tools-and-labels/products-labelling-rules-and-requirements/sustainable-products/about-sustainable-products_en.

- [24] "European Commission - Renewable Energy Directive," 2021. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/energy/topics/renewable-energy/directive-targets-and-rules/renewable-energy-directive_en#directive-2018-2001-eu.
- [25] F. J. S. Pacheco-Torgal, "Earth construction: Lessons from the past for future eco-efficient construction,," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 29, pp. 512-519, 2012.
- [26] B. V. M. J.-C. F. P. F. P. O. D. V. S. I. W. P. M. P. Reddy, "Codes and Standards on Earth Construction. In: Fabbri, A., Morel, J.C., Aubert, J.E., Bui, Q.B., Gallipoli, D., Reddy, B.V. (eds) Testing and Characterisation of Earth-based Building Materials and Elements. RILEM State-of-the-Art," *Codes and Standards on Earth Construction. In: Fabbri, A., Morel, J.C., Aubert, J.E., Bui, Q.B., Gallipoli, D., Reddy, B.V. (eds) Testing and Characterisation of Earth-based Building Materials and Elements. RILEM State-of-the-Art Reports*, vol 35. Springer, vol. 35, 2022.
- [27] H. Schroeder, "The New DIN Standards in Earth Building—The Current Situation in Germany," *Journal of Civil Engineering and Architecture*, vol. 12, pp. 113-120, 2018.
- [28] H. Schroeder, *Sustainable Building with Earth*, Springer International Publishing, 2016.
- [29] S. H, "4 - Modern earth building codes, standards and normative development,," in *In Woodhead Publishing Series in Energy, Modern Earth Buildings*, Woodhead Publishing,, 2012, pp. 72-109.
- [30] M. J. Delgado and I. Guerrero, "The selection of soils for unstabilised earth building: A normative review,," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 237-251, 2005.
- [31] J. Cid, F. Mazarron and I. Canas, "Las normativas de construcción con tierra en el mundo. The earth building normative documents in the world," *Informes de la Construcción*, vol. 63, no. 523, pp. 159-169, 2011.
- [32] S. I.-u. A.-V. S. (Hrsg.), "SIA Dokumentationen D 077,Bauen mit Lehm (1991); Schaerer, A., Huber, A., Kleespies, T.: D 0111, Regeln zum Bauen mit Lehm (1994); Hugli, H., Huber, A., Kleespies, T.: D 0112, Lehmbauatlas (1994); Hugli H., Huber, A., Kleespies, T".Zürich: SIA.
- [33] AFNOR, "Compressed earth blocks for walls and partitions: definitions –specifications – test methods – delivery acceptance conditions," AFNOR XP.P13-901, St Denis de la Plaine, France AFNOR., 2001.
- [34] A. E. d. N. y. C. (AENOR), "Bloques de tierra comprimada para muros y tabiques. Definiciones, especificaciones y métodos de ensayo. UNE 41410," 2008.

- [35] M. d. O. P. y. T. (MOPT 1992), "Bases para el diseño y construcción con tapial,," Secretaría General Técnica, 1992.
- [36] D. 1. German Institute for Standardization, "Earth blocks - Terms and definitions, requirements, test methods," 2013.
- [37] J. F. A. M. J. M. P. Aubert, "An earth block with a compressive strength higher than 45MPa!," Constr. Build. Mater, vol. 47, pp. 366-369, 2013.
- [38] J. E. Aubert , P. Maillard and J. C. Morel, "Towards a simple compressive strength test for earth bricks?," Materials and Structures, vol. 49, pp. 1641-1654, 2016.
- [39] D. 1. German Institute of Standardization, "Earth masonry mortar-Terms and definitions, requirements, test methods," 2013.
- [40] CEN, "Methods of test for mortar for masonry," EN 1015 1-21, 2002.
- [41] CEN, "EN 1015-3. Methods of test for mortar for masonry-part 3: Determination of consistence of fresh mortar (by flow table).," 1999.
- [42] CEN, "Methods of test for mortar for masonry Part 11: Determination of flexural and compressive strength of hardened mortar," EN 1015-11, 1999.
- [43] D. 1. German Institute of Standardization, "Earth plasters-Terms and definitions, requirements, test methods," 2013.
- [44] D. L. e. (Hrsg.), "Lehmbau Regeln—Begriffe, Baustoffe, Bauteile, 3., über überarbeitete Aufl . Vieweg+Teubner/GWV Fachverlage, Wiesbaden," 2009.
- [45] R. a. F. J. Gomes, "Earth use as building material (in Portuguese)," Circular de Informação Técnica N.º 9, Série D-4. . National Laboratory for Civil Engineering. , 1953.
- [46] R. Piemonte, "L.R. 2/06 (2006) Norme per la valorizzazione delle costruzioni in terra cruda, B.U.R. Piemonte, n° 3," 2006.
- [47] "Legge 24 Dicembre n. 378 (2003). Disposizioni per la tutela e la valorizzazione dell'architettura rurale.," Gazzetta Ufficiale, n° 13 , 2004.

- [48] Office of Energy Efficiency & Renewable Energy, "National Definition of a Zero Emissions BuildingPart 1: Operational Emissions from Energy Use, Version 1," June 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.energy.gov/eere/buildings/articles/national-definition-zero-emissions-building>.
- [49] European Commission, "European Commission, Proposal for the review of the CPR," 2022. [Online]. Available: https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/construction/construction-products-regulation-cpr/review_en, The Commission Proposal: Presentation 06/2022.
- [50] "European Commission - Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation," [Online]. Available: https://commission.europa.eu/energy-climate-change-environment/standards-tools-and-labels/products-labelling-rules-and-requirements/sustainable-products/ecodesign-sustainable-products-regulation_en#timeline.
- [51] "Supporting study for the Review of the Construction Products Regulation: Evaluation - Final Report".
- [52] PLURAL Project (GA No. 958218), 2021, D1.2 – Technical and market codes, national and European certification frameworks, [Phttps://www.plural-renovation.eu/publications-promo](https://www.plural-renovation.eu/publications-promo) (last accessed 13 April 2026).
- [53] M. Kjendseth Wiik, Developing whole-life carbon benchmark values for Norwegian buildings, pp 345-358, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09613218.2024.2445843>

9 Annex

9.1 Annex I

In Annex I, materials, structures and systems of DC#1 are presented in table matched with their respective regulation and standards in the columns to the right.

TABLE 9.1: LOAD BEARING STRUCTURES OF DC#1 AND RESPECTIVE REGULATION FRAMEWORK

	<i>Structural Type/Method/System</i>	<i>Main materials</i>		<i>Related Legislation/Regulation</i>				<i>Greenest related SP</i>	<i>Whole building related regulations</i>
		<i>Conventional / Commercial</i>	<i>Innovative / Recycled</i>	<i>National</i>	<i>European</i>	<i>Standardization ENs</i>	<i>Certified - Y/N</i>		
FOUNDATION			point foundation: steel and recycled concrete	DIN 4226-101:2017-08: Recycled aggregates for concrete in accordance with DIN EN 12620 - Part 101: Types and regulated dangerous substances; DIN 4226-102:2017-08: Recycled aggregates for concrete in accordance with DIN EN 12620 - Part 102: Type testing and factory production control	EC2 + national annex	DIN EN 1992-1-1: Eurocode 2: Design of concrete structures - Part 1-1: General rules and rules for buildings; DIN EN 1992-1-1 + NA: Eurocode 2: National Annex - Nationally determined parameter; DIN EN 206:2021-06: Concrete - Specification, performance, production and conformity	tbc.		Building code for Berlin (BauOBln) Administrative Provisions – Technical Building Rules (VVTB-Bln, 2024)
LOAD BEARING WALLS	Main load bearing system	external wall: timber panelled construction; bracing & elevator walls: solid timber walls	bracing & elevator walls: cross laminated timber	external wall: reclaimed waste-wood KVH structural timber DIN 4074-1:2012-06; DIN 4074-2:2021-01; DIN 4074-3:2008-12; DIN 4074-4:2008-12; DIN 4074-5:2008-12: Strength grading of wood	Circular Economy Act (KrWG); AltholzV: Ordinance on Requirements for the Recycling and Elimination of Waste Wood Directive 2008/98/EC: European Waste Framework Directive EC5 + national annex	(DIN) EN 1995-1-1:2010-12: Eurocode 5: Design of timber structures - Part 1-1: General - Common rules and rules for buildings; (DIN) EN 1995-1-1/NA: 2013-08: Eurocode 5: National Annex - Nationally determined parameters	tbc.	SP2 / SP7	Guideline for fire protection requirements in timber construction (MHolzBauRL); Regulation 305/2011/EC: Construction Products Regulation (CPR)

	Adhesive/connecting materials-mortars							NO	
	Reinforcements	steel cross in large glass facade	steel						
	Diaphragm	wood	wood-panel						
FRAMES	Main load bearing system	timber frame: lattice grid & solid wood columns		lattice grid with reclaimed waste-wood, laminated timber columns with reclaimed waste-wood	Circular Economy Act (KrWG); AltholzV: Ordinance on Requirements for the Recycling and Elimination of Waste Wood DIN 4074-1:2012-06; DIN 4074-2:2021-01; DIN 4074-3:2008-12; DIN 4074-4:2008-12; DIN 4074-5:2008-12; Strength grading of wood	Directive 2008/98/EC: European Waste Framework Directive		tbc.	SP2 / SP7
	Lateral load bearing system								
ROOF	Main load bearing system	SP 3 - solid timber slabs (flat roof)		WDLT-Slab (C24)	Circular Economy Act (KrWG); AltholzV: Ordinance on Requirements for the Recycling and Elimination of Waste Wood DIN 4074-1:2012-06; DIN 4074-2:2021-01; DIN 4074-3:2008-12; DIN 4074-4:2008-12; DIN 4074-5:2008-12; Strength grading of wood	Directive 2008/98/EC: European Waste Framework Directive		tbc.	SP2 / SP7
	Secondary load bearing system								
	Sheathing material								

	Diaphragm/ lateral rigidity	SP 3 - solid timber slabs (flat roof)		WDLT-Slab (C24)	Circular Economy Act (KrWG); AltholzV: Ordinance on Requirements for the Recycling and Elimination of Waste Wood DIN 4074-1:2012-06; DIN 4074-2:2021-01; DIN 4074-3:2008-12; DIN 4074-4:2008-12; DIN 4074-5:2008-12: Strength grading of wood	Directive 2008/98/EC: European Waste Framework Directive		tbc.	SP2 / SP7
	Structural battens and cross battens								
CEILINGS / SLABS	Main load bearing system	SP3 (WDLT-Slab)		WDLT-Slab (C24)	Circular Economy Act (KrWG); AltholzV: Ordinance on Requirements for the Recycling and Elimination of Waste Wood DIN 4074-1:2012-06; DIN 4074-2:2021-01; DIN 4074-3:2008-12; DIN 4074-4:2008-12; DIN 4074-5:2008-12: Strength grading of wood	Directive 2008/98/EC: European Waste Framework Directive		tbc.	SP2 / SP7
	Secondary load bearing system								
SLAB - FLOOR	Main load bearing system	solid structural timber	KVH structural timber						
	Secondary load bearing system								
	Diaphragm	solid timber	wood-panel						

TABLE 9.2: NON-LOAD BEARING STRUCTURES OF DC#1 AND RESPECTIVE REGULATION FRAMEWORK

	<i>Structural Type/Method/System</i>	<i>Main materials</i>		<i>Related Legislation/Regulation</i>				<i>Greenest related SP</i>	<i>Whole building related regulations</i>
		<i>Conventional / Commercial</i>	<i>Innovative / Recycled</i>	<i>National</i>	<i>European</i>	<i>Standardization ENs</i>	<i>Certified - Y/N</i>		
EXTERNAL WALLS	facade, outer layer	textile facade	textile facade (PTFE-coated fibreglass, PVC polyester); supporting steel structure						Building code for Berlin (BauOBl)
	Air Gap	vertical ventilation	400mm air gap						Administrative Provisions – Technical Building Rules (VVTB-Bln, 2024)
	external cladding or rendering, water proofing	timber cladding	timber	reclaimed waste-wood			(DIN) EN 13171:2015-04: Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made wood fibre (WF) products - Specification	YES	SP2 / SP7

	Air Gap/substructure	batten / counter batten	timber batten	reclaimed waste-wood	Circular Economy Act (KrWG); AltholzV: Ordinance on Requirements for the Recycling and Elimination of Waste Wood DIN 4074-1:2012-06; DIN 4074-2:2021-01; DIN 4074-3:2008-12; DIN 4074-4:2008-12; DIN 4074-5:2008-12: Strength grading of wood	Directive 2008/98/EC: European Waste Framework Directive		tbc.	SP2 / SP7	DIN 4108: Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings DIN 4109: Sound insulation in buildingsEnEV-Nachweises
	outer paneling	supporting panel, windtight layer	wood fibre board							
	skeleton	timber frame studs	timber	reclaimed waste-wood	Circular Economy Act (KrWG); AltholzV: Ordinance on Requirements for the Recycling and Elimination of Waste Wood DIN 4074-1:2012-06; DIN 4074-2:2021-01; DIN 4074-3:2008-12; DIN 4074-4:2008-12; DIN 4074-5:2008-12: Strength grading of wood	ECS + national annex	(DIN) EN 1995-1-1:2010-12: Eurocode 5: Design of timber structures - Part 1-1: General - Common rules and rules for buildings; (DIN) EN 1995-1-1/NA: 2013-08: Eurocode 5: National Annex - Nationally determined parameters	tbc.	SP2 / SP7	
	Thermal Insulation	SP 1 KARZ / blow-in insulation	wood fiber insulation	KARZ (SP1)			(DIN) EN 13171:2015-04: Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made wood fibre (WF) products - Specification	YES	SP1	

non bearing INTERNAL WALLS	material of the skeleton	solid timber frame walls	crosslaminated timber	crosslaminated timber from waste-wood	Circular Economy Act (KrWG); AltholzV: Ordinance on Requirements for the Recycling and Elimination of Waste Wood DIN 4074-1:2012-06; DIN 4074-2:2021-01; DIN 4074-3:2008-12; DIN 4074-4:2008-12; DIN 4074-5:2008-12: Strength grading of wood	EC5 + national annex	(DIN) EN 1995-1-1:2010-12: Eurocode 5: Design of timber structures - Part 1-1: General - Common rules and rules for buildings; (DIN) EN 1995-1-1/NA: 2013-08: Eurocode 5: National Annex - Nationally determined parameters	tbc.	SP2 / SP7	
	internal cladding or plastering	plaster	wood fiber board with earthen plaster							
OPENINGS	Window & Door - Frames	frames	wood-aluminum							
	Window & Door Openings - Glazing		triple sun-protection glazing							
	Shading	external shading	textile facade: PTFE-coated fiberglass, PVC polyester							
ROOF	Thermal Insulation	(blow-in) insulation	wood fibre insulation							
	Sub-layer									
	Waterproofing Material	sealing	rootresistant natural rubber							
	Air Gap	water draining layer	fleece filter							

	Roof covering	intensive green roof on substrate, water retention box	intensive green roof substrate						
CEILING	Acoustic insulation	acoustic panel	wood, felt, naturebased materials						
	Thermal Insulation	installation layer/fill	(blow-in) insulation wood fiber						
	Waterproofing Material								
	Sheathing								
	floor covering material	SP 3 Earth-Screed	Stabilized Earth	<p>DIN 18942-1:2024-03: Earthen materials and products - Part 1: Vocabulary;</p> <p>DIN 18942-100:2024-03: Earthen materials and products - Part 100: Conformity assessment;</p> <p>DIN 18948:2024-03: Earthen boards - Requirements, test and labelling;</p> <p>DIN 18947:2024-03: Earth plasters - Requirements, test and labelling;</p>	<p>German DIN possibly. Relevant basis at European level, ECJ ruling on excavation</p>		tbc.	SP3	
FLOOR	Sub flooring		timber; recycled aggregates						
	Thermal Insulation	insulation panels	wood fibre						
	Acoustic insulation	insulation panels	wood fibre						

9.2 Annex II

In Annex II, materials and structures of DC#2 are presented in table matched with their respective regulation and standards in the columns to the right (For this specific DC only data for the non-load bearing wall structure which is actually the EcoTechWall is given).

TABLE 9.3: NON-LOAD BEARING STRUCTURES OF DC#2 – ECOTECHWALL AND RESPECTIVE REGULATION FRAMEWORK

	<i>Structural Type/Method/System</i>	<i>Main materials</i>		<i>Related Legislation/Regulation</i>				<i>Greenest related SP</i>	<i>Whole building related regulations</i>	
		<i>Conventional / Commercial</i>	<i>Innovative / Recycled</i>	<i>National</i>	<i>European</i>	<i>Standardization ENs</i>	<i>Certified - Y/N</i>			
EcoTechWall	External cladding or rendering	water draining layer / metal or timber cladding	corrugated sheet metal	reused waste-wood (tbc.)	Circular Economy Act (KrWG); AltholzV: Ordinance on Requirements for the Recycling and Elimination of Waste Wood DIN 4074-1:2012-06; DIN 4074-2:2021-01; DIN 4074-3:2008-12; DIN 4074-4:2008-12; DIN 4074-5:2008-12: Strength grading of wood	Directive 2008/98/EC: European Waste Framework Directive		tbc.	SP11	Building code for Berlin (BauOBln) Administrative Provisions – Technical Building Rules (VVTB-Bln, 2024) Guideline for fire protection requirements in timber construction (MHolzBauRL); Regulation 305/2011/EC: Construction Products Regulation (CPR)
	Air Gap / Substructure	batten / counter batten	timber	reused waste-wood (tbc.)	Circular Economy Act (KrWG); AltholzV: Ordinance on Requirements for the Recycling and Elimination of Waste Wood DIN 4074-1:2012-06; DIN 4074-2:2021-01; DIN 4074-3:2008-12; DIN 4074-4:2008-12; DIN 4074-5:2008-12: Strength grading of wood	Directive 2008/98/EC: European Waste Framework Directive		tbc.	SP11	Energy performance of buildings directive (EPBD) Buildings Energy Act (GEG) DIN 4108: Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings DIN 4109: Sound insulation in buildings

	Fire protective layer if needed (tbc.)	non combustible board	gypsum board	clay board (tbc.)	<p>DIN 18942-100:2024-03: Earthen materials and products - Part 100: Conformity assessment;</p> <p>DIN 18948:2024-03: Earthen boards - Requirements, test and labelling;</p> <p>DIN 4102-1:1998-05; DIN 4102-2:1977-09; DIN 4102-4 : 2016-05: Fire behaviour of building materials and building components</p>		(DIN) EN 13501-1:2019-05: Fire classification of construction products and building elements - Part 1: Classification using data from reaction to fire tests	YES	SP11
	Outer panelling	supporting panel, windtight layer	wood fibre board				(DIN) EN 13171:2015-04: Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made wood fibre (WF) products - Specification	YES	SP11
	Skeleton	timber frame studs	timber	reused waste-wood (tbc.)	<p>Circular Economy Act (KrWG);</p> <p>AltholzV: Ordinance on Requirements for the Recycling and Elimination of Waste Wood</p> <p>DIN 4074-1:2012-06; DIN 4074-2:2021-01; DIN 4074-3:2008-12; DIN 4074-4:2008-12; DIN 4074-5:2008-12: Strength grading of wood</p>	EC5 + national annex	<p>(DIN) EN 1995-1-1:2010-12: Eurocode 5: Design of timber structures - Part 1-1: General - Common rules and rules for buildings;</p> <p>(DIN) EN 1995-1-1/NA: 2013-08: Eurocode 5: National Annex - Nationally determined parameters</p>	tbc.	SP11

Thermal Insulation	(blow-in)-insulation		recycled / nature based materials like cellulose or straw (tbc.)			(DIN) EN 13171:2015-04: Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made wood fibre (WF) products - Specification (DIN) EN 12086:2013-06: Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of water vapour transmission properties;	YES	SP11	
	Inner panelling	supporting panel, airtight layer	wood fibre hard board	(diagonal) timber board from waste wood (tbc.)	Circular Economy Act (KrWG); AltholzV: Ordinance on Requirements for the Recycling and Elimination of Waste Wood DIN 4074-1:2012-06; DIN 4074-2:2021-01; DIN 4074-3:2008-12; DIN 4074-4:2008-12; DIN 4074-5:2008-12: Strength grading of wood	Directive 2008/98/EC: European Waste Framework Directive	(DIN) EN 13986: Wood-based panels for use in construction - Characteristics, evaluation of conformity and marking	tbc.	SP11
	internal cladding or plastering	surface finish		earth plaster on plaster base / carrier (tbc.)	DIN 18942-1:2024-03: Earthen materials and products - Part 1: Vocabulary; DIN 18942-100:2024-03: Earthen materials and products - Part 100: Conformity assessment; DIN 18948:2024-03: Earthen boards - Requirements, test and labelling;			YES	SP11

					DIN 18947:2024-03: Earth plasters - Requirements, test and labelling					
OPENINGS	Openings - Frames									
	Openings - Glazing									
	Opaque openings (doors)									
	Shading									
ROOF	Thermal Insulation									
	Sub-layer									
	Waterproofing Material									
	Air Gap									
	Roof covering									
FLOOR	floor covering material									
	Sub flooring									
	Thermal Insulation									
	Acoustic insulation									

9.3 Annex III

In Annex III, materials, structures and systems of DC#4 are presented in table matched with their respective regulation and standards in the columns to the right.

TABLE 9.4: LOAD BEARING STRUCTURES OF DC#4 AND RESPECTIVE REGULATION FRAMEWORK

		<i>Structural Type/Method/System</i>	<i>Main materials</i>		<i>Related Legislation/Regulation</i>				<i>Greenest related SP</i>	<i>Whole building related regulations</i>
			<i>Conventional / Commercial</i>	<i>Innovative / Naturebased - Biobased - Recycled</i>	<i>National</i>	<i>European</i>	<i>Standardization ENs</i>	<i>Certified - Y/N</i>		
FOUNDATIONS		Reinforced Concrete Beams	C25/30	Reinforced with Recycled Steel	EΚΩΣ 2000/2003 EAK 2000/2003 ΚΤΣ 2016 ΚΤΧ 2008	EC2 NATIONAL ANNEXES				NEW BUILDING CONSTRUCTIONS REGULATION GREEK ANTI-SEISMIC REGULATION Greek Regulation of Reinforced Concrete & Regulation of Concrete Technology BUILDING FIRE PROTECTION REGULATION Terms, measures and program for alternative management of waste materials from excavations, constructions and deconstructions (Joint Ministerial Decision 36259/1757/E103/2010)
LOAD BEARING WALLS	Main load bearing system	Stone		Limestone		EC6, EC8 NATIONAL ANNEXES		YES		
	Adhesive/connecting materials-mortars	Mortar	Mortar	Earthbased		EC6 NATIONAL ANNEXES		NO		
	Reinforcements	Concrete Beams	C25/30		EΚΩΣ 2000/2003 EAK 2000/2003 ΚΤΣ 2016 ΚΤΧ 2008	EC6, EC2, EC8 NATIONAL ANNEXES			SP9	
	Diaphragm					EC5, EC8 NATIONAL ANNEXES				
FRAMES	Main load bearing system	Stone & Timber Frame				EC5, EC8 NATIONAL ANNEXES				
	Lateral load bearing system					EC3, EC8 NATIONAL ANNEXES				
COLUMN		Stone & Timber				EC5 NATIONAL ANNEXES			SP9	
ROOF	Main load bearing system	Timber Frame		Recycled Timber		EC5 NATIONAL ANNEXES				
						EC5 NATIONAL ANNEXES				

	Secondary load bearing system	Timber Purlins	Solid Wood	Recycled Timber		EC5 NATIONAL ANNEXES			
	Sheathing material					EC5 NATIONAL ANNEXES			
	Diaphragm/ lateral rigidity					EC5, EC8 NATIONAL ANNEXES			
	Structural battens and cross battens					EC5 NATIONAL ANNEXES			
CEILING - ROOF LEVEL	Main load bearing system	Timber Beams	Solid Wood	Recycled Timber		EC5 NATIONAL ANNEXES			
	Secondary load bearing system					EC5 NATIONAL ANNEXES			
FLOOR	Main load bearing system	Earth & Stone				EC5 NATIONAL ANNEXES			
	Secondary load bearing system	Concrete				EC5 NATIONAL ANNEXES			
	Diaphragm					EC5, EC8 NATIONAL ANNEXES			

TABLE 9.5: NON -LOAD BEARING STRUCTURES OF DC#4 AND RESPECTIVE REGULATION FRAMEWORK

	Structural Type/Method/System	Main materials		Related Legislation/Regulation				Greenest related SP	Whole building related regulations
		Conventional / Commercial	Innovative / Naturebased - Biobased - Recycled	National	European	Standardization ENs	Certified - Y/N		
WALLS	Material of the skeleton			(KENAK) GREEK REGULATION ON THE ENERGY PERFORMANCE OF BUILDINGS					(KENAK) GREEK REGULATION ON THE ENERGY PERFORMANCE OF BUILDINGS BUILDING FIRE PROTECTION REGULATION BUILDING STRUCTURES REGULATION
	Thermal Insulation							SP9	
	Water proofing								
	Air Gap								
	external cladding or rendering								
	internal cladding or plastering								
OPENINGS	Openings - Frames	Timber Frame Openings	Recycled Timber		EN 14351				
	Openings - Glazing	Double Glazed		Technical Guides of Technical Chamber of Greece for window glazing	EN 356, EN 572, EN 1279-1-6, EN 12150-1-2				
	Opaque openings (doors)	Timber Doors	Recycled Timber						
	Shading								
ROOF	Thermal Insulation								
	Sub-layer								
	Waterproofing Material								

	Air Gap									
	Roof covering	Ceramic Tiles	Tiles							
CEILING - ROOF LEVEL	material of the skeleton									
	Thermal Insulation									
	Waterproofing Material									
	Sheathing									
FLOOR	floor covering material	Timber & Oak	Planks	Recycled Timber						
	Sub flooring									
	Thermal Insulation									
	Acoustic insulation									
CEILING - FLOOR	Material of the skeleton	Timber		Recycled Timber						
	Sheathing									

